

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4000–4133

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0037

Cover photo

Mosaic of MAHLI focus merge products showing a stratified and fractured rock outcrop at the Mineral King/Mineral King3 drill site named Observation Peak. The images, illuminated by sunlight from the upper right, were acquired on Sol 4105 and merged on Sol 4106.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 4000th and 4133rd Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 4000 and 4133.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA's MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator's Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4000–4133*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 36 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 06 November 2023 through 23 March 2024.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report's period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 4000 through 4133 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4000 – 4133						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At the Sequoia drill site	Solar Conjunction period (Sols 4001 to 4022) – The Sequoia2 sample remained inside the drill bit assembly throughout the Solar Conjunction period; MAHLI was not operated during this time. The sample held by the drill bit assembly was discarded on Sol 4024.					
	05 Dec 23	4028	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the Sequoia2 drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.
Driving towards Fascination Turret of the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge	07 Dec 23	4030	5	34	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Keeler_Needle and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.
	10 Dec 23	4032	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Wren_Peak. The Robotic Arm faulted after the acquisition of the 15 cm standoff image of Wren_Peak, which precluded the rest of the Sol 4032 MAHLI activities and left MAHLI with the dust cover open above the target.
	10 Dec 23	4033	0	0	4	A fault occurred onboard the rover on Sol 4032 that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the DRT-brushed target Wren_Peak; instead, the focus stack images from Sol 4030 imaging of Keeler_Needle and Sol 4028 imaging of APXS spot 2 of Sequoia2 drill cuttings were merged again.
	13 Dec 23	4035	4	32	3	The MAHLI dust cover was closed after the Sol 4032 Robotic Arm fault. MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Wren_Peak (brushed on Sol 4032) and the focus stack images were merged.
	15 Dec 23	4037	3	6	0	MAHLI imaged the target Potluck_Pass.
	17 Dec 23	4039	10	60	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Arrow_Peak and the target Four_Gables.
	18 Dec 23	4040	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4039 were merged.
	31 Dec 23	4053	15	92	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Moose_Lake and the target Lewis_Creek. MAHLI also imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding.
Driving towards Fascination Turret of the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge	01 Jan 24	4054	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4053 were merged.
	03 Jan 24	4056	12	69	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Green_Pass and Wanda_Lake. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	04 Jan 24	4057	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4056 were merged.
	09 Jan 24	4062	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Chagoopa and the focus stack images were merged.
	15 Jan 24	4067	6	44	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Spilt_Mountain and Great_Western_Divide.
	15 Jan 24	4068	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4067 were merged.
	18 Jan 24	4070	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Scheelite and Dorst.
19 Jan 24	4071	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4070 were merged.	

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4000 – 4133						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving towards Fascination Turret of the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge	21 Jan 24	4073	9	66	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Mount_Langley and the target Sleeping_Beautys_Tower.
	21 Jan 24	4074	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4073 were merged.
	24 Jan 24	4076	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Manzanita and the focus stack images were merged.
	26 Jan 24	4078	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Sierra_Columbine and the focus stack images were merged.
	27 Jan 24	4079	8	64	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Simpson_Meadow and Lake_Sabrina. The focus stack images were also merged.
	30 Jan 24	4082	13	90	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target June_Lake, the target Deerhorn_Mountain and the DRT-brushed target Martha_Lake.
	31 Jan 24	4083	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4082 were merged.
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge near Fascination Turret	01 Feb 24	4084	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Grizzly_Lakes and the focus stack images were merged.
	05 Feb 24	4088	20	20	0	MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
	06 Feb 24	4089	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the target Willow_Springs, which included a checkout of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.
	10 Feb 24	4093	16	72	5	MAHLI imaged the target Iridescent_Lake and DRT-brushed target The_Miter. A test to see how the performance of the DRT compares at different distances above the surface of a target was done on the target The_Miter. The DRT was used to brush the target The_Miter at the height of 19 mm standoff, 17 mm standoff and the standard height of 15 mm standoff. MAHLI was used to document the surface before it was brushed and after the three brush events. The focus stack images were also merged.
	15 Feb 24	4098	10	44	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Horseshoe_Meadows, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.
	18 Feb 24	4101	7	46	0	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV sensor, the target Thunderbolt_Peak and the target Tenderfoot_Peak.
	19 Feb 24	4102	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4101 were merged.
At Mineral_King/Mineral_King3 Drill Site	22 Feb 24	4105	13	114	0	MAHLI acquired a 7x1 mosaic on the target Observation_Peak. MAHLI also imaged the intended drill target Mineral_King after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. For position 7 of the Observation_Peak mosaic, the distance to the target was greater than anticipated and the camera was unable to find focus; thus, none of the images for that position have in-focus elements.
	23 Feb 24	4106	0	0	11	Focus stack images from Sol 4105 were merged.
At Mineral_King/Mineral_King3 Drill Site	05 Mar 24	4116	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the Mineral_King drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.
	06 Mar 24	4117	6	9	0	MAHLI imaged the Mineral_King drill hole cuttings. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	07 Mar 24	4118	6	44	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mineral_King2 after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4000 – 4133						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At Mineral_King/ Mineral_King3 Drill Site	12 Mar 24	4123	6	44	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mineral_King3 after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.
	16 Mar 24	4127	3	14	0	MAHLI imaged the attempted (Sol 4125) Mineral_King3 drill hole and drill cuttings.
	17 Mar 24	4128	1	2	1	MAHLI imaged the attempted (Sol 4125) Mineral_King3 drill cuttings. The focus stack images from Sol 4127 were merged.
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge near Fascination Turret	19 Mar 24	4130	6	52	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Tunnel_View and acquired a 2x1 mosaic on the target Cardinal_Mountain. The focus stack images were merged as well.
	21 Mar 24	4132	7	62	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Three_Teeth_Doodad and the target Col_de_Doodad. The focus stack images were merged as well.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 000158001

product type
as received from Mars → 10101221C00

sequence ID → 000158001

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 000158001

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 000158001

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → 10101221C00

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → 10101221C00

Note: Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is not always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 4000–4133 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 4028, 4030, 4032, 4035, 4037, 4039, 4053, 4056, 4062, 4067, 4070, 4073, 4076, 4078, 4079, 4082, 4084, 4088, 4089, 4093, 4098, 4101, 4105, 4116, 4117, 4118, 4123, 4127, 4128, 4130, 4132.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{\text{uncertainty}} = (p_{\text{far}} + p_{\text{near}})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4028 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Sequoia2 drill hole

Sequoia2 drill hole													
mhl100197	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4028MH0001970011403185C00	3185	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8
mhl100774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm										
	4028MH0007740011403187C00	3187	13529	11.4	9.5	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.6

Sequoia2 drill hole cuttings

Sequoia2 drill hole cuttings														
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1													
	4028MH0001520011403189C00	3189	13935	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4028MH0002650001403210R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4028MH0002650001403211S00					
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2													
	4028MH0001520011403199C00	3199	13925	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4028MH0002650001403208R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4028MH0002650001403209S00					
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4033MH0001530001403260R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4033MH0001530001403261S00					

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		

target named Keeler_Needle – after DRT

target named Keeler_Needle – after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	4030MH0001900011403213C00	3213	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4030MH0001680011403215C00	3215	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4030MH0001930001403250R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4030MH0001930001403251S00					
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4033MH0001530001403258R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4033MH0001530001403259S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4030MH0001680011403225C00	3225	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4030MH0001930001403248R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4030MH0001930001403249S00					
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4033MH0001530001403256R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4033MH0001530001403257S00					
mhl100184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm											
	4030MH0001840011403235C00	3235	14689	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4030MH0001930001403246R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4030MH0001930001403247S00					
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4033MH0001530001403254R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4033MH0001530001403255S00					

REMS UV sensor

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	4030MH0000950011403245C00	3245	13258	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	65.9	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4032 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Wren_Peak - after DRT

SEQUENCE	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
mhli00586	4032MH0005860011403253C00	3253	13256	16.8	14.9	-0.8	0.8	66.1	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

UPDATED: 14_December_2023

SOL 4035 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Wren_Peak** – after sol 4032 DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4035MH0001900011403263C00	3263	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4035MH0001680011403265C00	3265	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4035MH0001930001403296R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4035MH0001930001403299S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4035MH0001680011403275C00	3275	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4035MH0001930001403296R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4035MH0001930001403297S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	4035MH0003020011403285C00	3285	14653	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4035MH0001930001403294R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4035MH0001930001403295S00	

UPDATED: 15_December_2023

SOL 4037 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Potluck_Pass														
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4037MH0001900011403301C00	3301	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6	
mhl00148	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4037MH0001480011403303C00	3303	13578	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4	
mhl00148	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4037MH0001480011403305C00	3305	13581	10.7	8.8	-0.3	0.3	44.6	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.3	

SOL 4039 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Arrow_Peak – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm														
mhli00190	4039MH0001900011403307C00		3307	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00168	4039MH0001680011403309C00		3309	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403374R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403375S00														
MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00168	4039MH0001680011403319C00		3319	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403372R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403373S00														
MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00705	4039MH0007050011403329C00		3329	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00705	4039MH0007050011403331C00		3331	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00705	4039MH0007050011403333C00		3333	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm														
mhli00743	4039MH0007430011403335C00		3335	14871	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403370R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403371S00														

target named Four_Gables

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm														
mhli00190	4039MH0001900011403345C00		3345	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00297	4039MH0002970011403347C00		3347	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403368R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403369S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
mhli00297	4039MH0002970011403357C00		3357	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403366R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4040MH0002270001403367S00														

SOL 4053 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Moose_Lake - after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4053MH0001900011403377C00	3377	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0001680011403379C00	3379	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403478R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403479S00						
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0001680011403389C00	3389	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403476R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403477S00						
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	4053MH0007430011403399C00	3399	15083	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403474R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403475S00						

target named Lewis_Creek - quantitative relief model (QRM) data													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4053MH0001900011403409C00	3409	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100182	MED RES - STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0001820011403411C00	3411	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403472R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403473S00						
mhl100182	MED RES - STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0001820011403421C00	3421	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403470R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403471S00						
mhl100705	MED RES - RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0007050011403431C00	3431	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
mhl100705	MED RES - RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0007050011403433C00	3433	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100705	MED RES - RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4053MH0007050011403435C00	3435	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100426	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	4053MH0004260011403437C00	3437	15060	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403468R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4054MH0001630001403469S00						

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - first set													
NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.													
mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0007120001403446C00	3446	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0007120011403447C00	3447	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0007120021403448C00	3448	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0007120031403449C00	3449	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0007120041403450C00	3450	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - first set													
mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0004530001403451C00	3451	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0004530011403452C00	3452	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0004530021403453C00	3453	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0004530031403454C00	3454	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4053MH0004530041403455C00	3455	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4053MH0004530051403456C00	3456	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE..

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)														
mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0004530001403457C00	3457	15996	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0004530011403458C00	3458	14664	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0004530021403459C00	3459	13998	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0004530031403460C00	3460	13014	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0004530041403461C00	3461	12750	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS														
4053MH0004530051403462C00	3462	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)														
NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.														
mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0007120001403463C00	3463	0	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0007120011403464C00	3464	2412	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0007120021403465C00	3465	3078	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0007120031403466C00	3466	4062	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						
	INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4053MH0007120041403467C00	3467	4488	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a						

SOL 4056 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Green_Pass – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4056MH0001900011403481C00	3481	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4056MH0001680011403483C00	3483	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4057MH0001630001403559R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4057MH0001630001403560S00	
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4056MH0001680011403493C00	3493	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4057MH0001630001403557R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4057MH0001630001403558S00	
mhlI00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4056MH0007430011403503C00	3503	15066	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4057MH0001630001403559R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4057MH0001630001403556S00	

target named Wanda_Lake – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4056MH0001900011403513C00	3513	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4056MH0001680011403515C00	3515	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4057MH0001630001403553R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4057MH0001630001403554S00	
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4056MH0001680011403525C00	3525	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4057MH0001630001403551R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4057MH0001630001403552S00	
mhlI00302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	4056MH0003020011403535C00	3535	14648	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4057MH0001630001403549R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4057MH0001630001403550S00	

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhlI00312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4056MH0003120001403544C00	3544	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH												
mhlI00326	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm											
	4056MH0003120011403545C00	3545	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhlI00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
mhlI00326	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4056MH0003260001403546C00	3546	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhlI00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
mhlI00326	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4056MH0003260001403547C00	3547	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhlI00228	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm											
	4056MH0002280001403548C00	3548	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 10_January_2024

SOL 4062 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Chagoopa – after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4062MH0001900011403562C00	3562	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4062MH0001680011403564C00	3564	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4062MH0001930001403597R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4062MH0001930001403598S00								
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4062MH0001680011403574C00	3574	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4062MH0001930001403595R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4062MH0001930001403596S00								
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
	4062MH0003020011403584C00	3584	14711	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4062MH0001930001403593R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4062MH0001930001403594S00								

SOL 4067 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Split_Mountain**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	4067MH0001900011403600C00	3600	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4067MH0002240011403602C00	3602	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4068MH0001530001403649R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4068MH0001530001403650S00	
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4067MH0002240011403612C00	3612	13932	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4068MH0001530001403647R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4068MH0001530001403648S00	
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 3														
	4067MH0002240011403622C00	3622	13951	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4068MH0001530001403645R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4068MH0001530001403646S00	
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 4														
	4067MH0002240011403632C00	3632	13936	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4068MH0001530001403643R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4068MH0001530001403644S00	

target named **Great_Western_Divide**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 28 cm											
	4067MH0001900011403642C00	3642	12975	29.3	27.4	-2.1	2.5	110.1	8.1	1608	1198	17.7	13.2

SOL 4070 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Scheelite – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4070MH0001900011403652C00	3652	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4070MH0001680011403654C00	3654	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4071MH0001630001403725R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4071MH0001630001403726S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4070MH0001680011403664C00	3664	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4071MH0001630001403723R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4071MH0001630001403724S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4070MH0007430011403674C00	3674	15112	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4071MH0001630001403721R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4071MH0001630001403722S00

target named Dorst – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4070MH0001900011403684C00	3684	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4070MH0001820011403686C00	3686	13981	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4071MH0001630001403719R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4071MH0001630001403720S00
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4070MH0001820011403696C00	3696	13986	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4071MH0001630001403717R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4071MH0001630001403718S00
mhl100337	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	4070MH0003370011403706C00	3706	14640	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4071MH0001630001403715R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4071MH0001630001403716S00

SOL 4073 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Mount_Langley – after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4073MH0001900011403728C00	3728	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4073MH0001680011403730C00	3730	14048	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4074MH0001630001403803R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4074MH0001630001403804S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4073MH0001680011403740C00	3740	14050	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4074MH0001630001403801R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4074MH0001630001403802S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4073MH0007430011403750C00	3750	15251	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	15.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4074MH0001630001403799R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4074MH0001630001403800S00	

target named **Sleeping_Beautys_Tower**

mhl100190	CONTEXT STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4073MH0001900011403760C00	3760	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100190	CONTEXT STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4073MH0001900011403762C00	3762	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4073MH0001730011403764C00	3764	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4074MH0001630001403797R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4074MH0001630001403798S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4073MH0001730011403774C00	3774	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4074MH0001630001403795R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4074MH0001630001403796S00	
mhl100386	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4073MH0003860011403784C00	3784	15053	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4074MH0001630001403793R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4074MH0001630001403794S00	

UPDATED: 24_January_2024

SOL 4076 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Manzanita – after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4076MH0001900011403806C00	3806	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4076MH0001680011403808C00	3808	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4076MH0001930001403841R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4076MH0001930001403842S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4076MH0001680011403818C00	3818	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4076MH0001930001403839R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4076MH0001930001403840S00					
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm									
	4076MH0003020011403828C00	3828	14725	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4076MH0001930001403837R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4076MH0001930001403838S00					

UPDATED: 26_January_2024

SOL 4078 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <i>Sierra_Columbine</i> - after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4078MH0001900011403844C00	3844	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4078MH0001820011403846C00	3846	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4078MH0001930001403879R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4078MH0001930001403880S00
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4078MH0001820011403856C00	3856	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4078MH0001930001403877R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4078MH0001930001403878S00
mhl100796	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4078MH0007960011403866C00	3866	15046	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4078MH0001930001403875R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4078MH0001930001403876S00

SOL 4079 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Simpson_Meadow – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4079MH0001900011403882C00	3882	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4079MH0001680011403884C00	3884	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4079MH0001630001403955R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4079MH0001630001403956S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4079MH0001680011403894C00	3894	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4079MH0001630001403953R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4079MH0001630001403954S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	4079MH0003020011403904C00	3904	14697	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4079MH0001630001403951R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4079MH0001630001403952S00	

target named Lake_Sabrina – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4079MH0001900011403914C00	3914	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4079MH0001680011403916C00	3916	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4079MH0001630001403949R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4079MH0001630001403950S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4079MH0001680011403926C00	3926	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4079MH0001630001403947R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4079MH0001630001403948S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	4079MH0003020011403936C00	3936	14743	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4079MH0001630001403945R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4079MH0001630001403946S00	

SOL 4082 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named June_Lake – before DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4082MH0001900011403958C00	3958	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4082MH0001220011403960C00	3960	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named June_Lake – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4082MH0001900011403962C00	3962	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4082MH0001680011403964C00	3964	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404061R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404062S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4082MH0001680011403974C00	3974	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404059R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404060S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	4082MH0003020011403984C00	3984	14679	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404057R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404058S00	

target named Deerhorn_Mountain

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4082MH0001900011403994C00	3994	13035	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.6		
mhl100841	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm													
	4082MH0008410011403996C00	3996	13309	15.5	13.6	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404055R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404056S00	
mhl100841	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm													
	4082MH0008410011404006C00	4006	13307	15.5	13.6	-0.6	0.7	61.5	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404053R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404054S00	

target named Martha_Lake – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4082MH0001900011404016C00	4016	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4082MH0003360011404018C00	4018	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404051R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404052S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4082MH0003360011404028C00	4028	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404049R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404050S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4082MH0008480011404038C00	4038	15096	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404047R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4083MH0001700001404048S00	

UPDATED: 02_February_2024

SOL 4084 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Grizzly_Lakes** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4084MH0001900011404064C00	4064	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4084MH0001680011404066C00	4066	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4084MH0001930001404099R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4084MH0001930001404100S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4084MH0001680011404076C00	4076	14036	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4084MH0001930001404097R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4084MH0001930001404098S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4084MH0007430011404086C00	4086	15219	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4084MH0001930001404095R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4084MH0001930001404096S00

SOL 4088 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 4088)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4088MH0007690011404101E01	4101	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4088MH0007700011404102E01	4102	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4088MH0007710011404103E01	4103	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4088MH0007720011404104E01	4104	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 4088)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4088MH0007690011404105E01	4105	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4088MH0007700011404106E01	4106	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4088MH0007710011404107E01	4107	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4088MH0007720011404108E01	4108	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 4088)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4088MH0007690011404109E01	4109	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4088MH0007700011404110E01	4110	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4088MH0007710011404111E01	4111	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4088MH0007720011404112E01	4112	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 4088)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4088MH0007690011404113E01	4113	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4088MH0007700011404114E01	4114	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4088MH0007710011404115E01	4115	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4088MH0007720011404116E01	4116	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE..

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 4088)													
mhl00769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4088M0007690011404117E01	4117	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~-612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4088M0007700011404118E01	4118	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~-408	~-137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4088M0007710011404119E01	4119	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~-489	~-210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4088M0007720011404120E01	4120	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~-450	~-175	1608	1198	~72	~54

UPDATED: 15_February_2024

SOL 4089 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Willow_Springs

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm									
	4089MH0001900011404122C00	4122	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4089MH0001820011404124C00	4124	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4089MH0002650001404147R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4089MH0002650001404148S00					
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4089MH0001820011404134C00	4134	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4089MH0002650001404145R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4089MH0002650001404146S00					

target named Willow_Springs - MAHLI proximity mode checkout

mhl00866	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4089MH0008660011404144C00	4144	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

SOL 4093 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
target named Iridescent_Lake													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4093MH0001900011404150C00	4150	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001820011404152C00	4152	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4093MH0002270001404229R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4093MH0002270001404230S00					
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001820011404162C00	4162	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4093MH0002270001404227R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4093MH0002270001404228S00					
target named The_Miter – brush height test – before DRT													
mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm										
	4093MH0005860011404172C00	4172	13256	16.8	14.9	-0.8	0.8	66.1	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001220011404174C00	4174	13968	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001220011404176C00	4176	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
target named The_Miter – brush height test – after DRT from a height of 19 mm standoff													
mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm										
	4093MH0005860011404178C00	4178	13256	16.8	14.9	-0.8	0.8	66.1	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001220011404180C00	4180	13969	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001220011404182C00	4182	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
target named The_Miter – brush height test – after DRT from a height of 17 mm standoff													
mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm										
	4093MH0005860011404184C00	4184	13257	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	66.0	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001220011404186C00	4186	13954	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001220011404188C00	4188	13976	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
target named The_Miter – brush height test – after DRT from the standard height of 15 mm standoff													
mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4093MH0005860011404190C00	4190	13253	16.9	15.0	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	1608	1198	10.7	8.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001680011404192C00	4192	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4093MH0002270001404225R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4093MH0002270001404226S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4093MH0001680011404202C00	4202	13968	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4093MH0002270001404223R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4093MH0002270001404224S00					
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm										
	4093MH0003020011404212C00	4212	14589	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4093MH0002270001404221R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4093MH0002270001404222S00					

SOL 4098 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Horseshoe_Meadows – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4098MH0001900011404232C00	4232	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4098MH0001680011404234C00	4234	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4098MH0001930001404279R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4098MH0001930001404280S00	
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4098MH0001680011404244C00	4244	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4098MH0001930001404277R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4098MH0001930001404278S00	
mhlI00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4098MH0007430011404254C00	4254	15122	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4098MH0001930001404275R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4098MH0001930001404276S00	

target named Horseshoe_Meadows – MAHLI proximity mode – after DRT

mhlI00866	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4098MH0008660011404264C00	4264	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
mhlI00867	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 4 cm										
	4098MH0008670011404266C00	4266	14195	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
mhlI00868	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 3 cm										
	4098MH0008680011404268C00	4268	14420	4.7	2.8	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.8	2.8
mhlI00869	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm										
	4098MH0008690011404270C00	4270	14729	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
mhlI00870	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm										
	4098MH0008700011404272C00	4272	14907	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2
mhlI00871	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4098MH0008710011404274C00	4274	15106	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0

SOL 4101 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	4101MH0000950011404282C00	4282	13260	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.7	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

target named Thunderbolt_Peak															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4101MH0001900011404284C00	4284	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4101MH0001820011404286C00	4286	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4102MH0001530001404333R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4102MH0001530001404334S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4101MH0001820011404296C00	4296	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4102MH0001530001404331R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4102MH0001530001404332S00	

target named Tenderfoot_Peak															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4101MH0001900011404306C00	4306	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4101MH0001820011404308C00	4308	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4102MH0001530001404329R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4102MH0001530001404330S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4101MH0001820011404318C00	4318	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4102MH0001530001404327R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4102MH0001530001404328S00	

SOL 4105 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Observation_Peak** – a 7 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
POSITION 1 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404336C00	4336	12943	31.8	29.9	-2.5, 2.9	119.0	9.6	1608, 1198	19.1, 14.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404469R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404470S00										
POSITION 2 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404346C00	4346	12942	31.9	30.0	-2.5, 3.0	119.3	9.7	1608, 1198	19.2, 14.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404467R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404468S00										
POSITION 3 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404356C00	4356	12951	31.2	29.3	-2.4, 2.8	116.6	9.2	1608, 1198	18.8, 14.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404465R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404466S00										
POSITION 4 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404366C00	4366	12970	29.7	27.8	-2.2, 2.5	111.4	8.3	1608, 1198	17.9, 13.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404463R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404464S00										
POSITION 5 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404376C00	4376	12979	29.0	27.1	-2.1, 2.4	109.1	8.0	1608, 1198	17.5, 13.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404461R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404462S00										
POSITION 6 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404386C00	4386	12837	44.1	42.2	-4.7, 5.9	162.0	18.7	1608, 1198	26.1, 19.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404459R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404460S00										
POSITION 7 OF 7										
mhli00874	4105MH0008740011404396C00	4396	13416	13.2	11.3	-0.5, 0.5	53.5	1.7	1608, 1198	8.6, 6.4
NOTE: THE STANDOFF DISTANCE WAS GREATER THAN ANTICIPATED AND THE CAMERA WAS UNABLE TO FIND FOCUS; THUS, THE IMAGES DO NOT HAVE IN-FOCUS ELEMENTS CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404457R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404458S00										

intended drill target named **Mineral_King** – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
CONTEXT VIEW										
mhli00190	4105MH0001900011404406C00	4406	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7, 2.0	99.6	6.5	1608, 1198	16.0, 11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404456R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404456S00										
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1										
APXS RASTER SPOT 2										
mhli00336	4105MH0003360011404408C00	4408	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2, 0.2	30.7	0.5	1608, 1198	4.9, 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404453R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404453S00										
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2										
APXS RASTER SPOT 2										
mhli00336	4105MH0003360011404418C00	4418	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2, 0.1	30.4	0.5	1608, 1198	4.9, 3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404453R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404454S00										
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW										
APXS RASTER SPOT 2										
mhli00873	4105MH0008730011404428C00	4428	14723	3.7	1.8	-0.1, 0.1	20.0	0.3	1608, 1198	3.2, 2.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404451R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404452S00										
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW										
APXS RASTER SPOT 1										
mhli00336	4105MH0003360011404438C00	4438	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2, 0.2	30.8	0.5	1608, 1198	4.9, 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404449R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4106MH0004490001404450S00										

intended drill target named **Mineral_King** – after drill bit pre-load test

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
CONTEXT VIEW										
mhli00465	4105MH0004650011404448C00	4448	12897	36.3	34.4	-3.2, 3.9	134.5	12.5	1608, 1198	21.6, 16.1

UPDATED: 06_March_2024

SOL 4116 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Mineral_King drill hole

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100197	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	4116MH0001970011404472C00	4472	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhl100774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 10 cm										
	4116MH0007740011404474C00	4474	13545	11.2	9.3	-0.4	0.4	46.3	1.3	1608	1198	7.4	5.5

Mineral_King drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100152	APXS RASTER SPOT 1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4116MH0001520011404476C00	4476	14177	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4116MH0002650001404497R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4116MH0002650001404498S00			
mhl100152	APXS RASTER SPOT 2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4116MH0001520011404486C00	4486	14160	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4116MH0002650001404495R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4116MH0002650001404496S00			

SOL 4117 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Mineral_King drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100122	APXS RASTER SPOT 1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4117MH0001220011404500C00	4500	13985	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
mhl100122	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4117MH0001220011404502C00	4502	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4117MH0003120001404503C00	4503	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm												
mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH												
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4117MH0003120011404504C00	4504	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
	INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm												
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4117MH0003260001404505C00	4505	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm												
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4117MH0003260001404506C00	4506	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm												

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100228	4117MH0002280001404507C00	4507	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4118 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Mineral_King2 – after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4118MH0001900011404509C00	4509	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4118MH0001680011404511C00	4511	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4118MH0001530001404558R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4118MH0001530001404559S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4118MH0001680011404521C00	4521	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4118MH0001530001404556R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4118MH0001530001404557S00	
mhl00302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4118MH0003020011404531C00	4531	14711	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4118MH0001530001404554R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4118MH0001530001404555S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4118MH0001680011404541C00	4541	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4118MH0001530001404552R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4118MH0001530001404553S00	

intended drill target named Mineral_King2 – after drill bit pre-load test

mhl00465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	4118MH0004650011404551C00	4551	12896	36.4	34.5	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	1608	1198	21.7	16.2

UPDATED: 13_March_2024

SOL 4123 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Mineral_King3 – after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4123MH0001900011404561C00	4561	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4123MH0001680011404563C00	4563	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4123MH0001530001404610R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4123MH0001530001404611S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4123MH0001680011404573C00	4573	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4123MH0001530001404608R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4123MH0001530001404609S00	
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4123MH0007430011404583C00	4583	15113	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4123MH0001530001404606R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4123MH0001530001404607S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4123MH0001680011404593C00	4593	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4123MH0001530001404604R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4123MH0001530001404605S00	

intended drill target named Mineral_King3 – after drill bit pre-load test

mhl00465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	4123MH0004650011404603C00	4603	12895	36.5	34.6	-3.3	3.9	135.3	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.2

UPDATED: 18_March_2024

SOL 4127 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Mineral_King3 attempted drill hole

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100197	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4127MH0001970011404613C00	4613	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 10 cm											
	4127MH0007740011404615C00	4615	13502	11.8	9.9	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	1608	1198	7.8	5.8

Mineral_King3 attempted drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4127MH0002990011404617C00	4617	14150	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4128MH0002580001404628R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4128MH0002580001404629S00			

UPDATED: 18_March_2024

SOL 4128 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Mineral_King3 attempted drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhli00122	4128MH0001220011404627C00	4627	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

SOL 4130 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Tunnel_View** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4130MH0001900011404631C00	4631	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4130MH0001680011404633C00	4633	14046	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304690R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4130MH0002270001304691S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4130MH0001680011404643C00	4643	14055	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304688R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4130MH0002270001304689S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4130MH0007430011404653C00	4653	15264	2.5	0.6	0.0	0.1	15.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.5	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304686R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4130MH0002270001304687S00

target named **Cardinal_Mountain** – a 2 x 1 mosaic

mhl100865	POSITION 1 OF 2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4130MH0008650011404663C00	4663	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304684R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4130MH0002270001304685S00
mhl100865	POSITION 2 OF 2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4130MH0008650011304673C00	4673	13033	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304682R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4130MH0002270001304683S00

SOL 4132 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Three_Teeth_Doodad** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4132MH0001900011304693C00	4693	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4132MH0003360011204695C00	4695	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4132MH0001630000904764R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4132MH0001630000904765S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4132MH0003360011204705C00	4705	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4132MH0001630001004762R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4132MH0001630000904763S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4132MH0008640011204715C00	4715	15190	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4132MH0001630001004760R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4132MH0001630001004761S00

target named **CoL_de_Doodad**

mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4132MH0008650011204725C00	4725	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4132MH0001630001004758R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4132MH0001630001004759S00
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4132MH0008650011204735C00	4735	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4132MH0001630001004756R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4132MH0001630001004757S00
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4132MH0008650011004745C00	4745	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4132MH0001630001004754R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4132MH0001630001004755S00

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 4000–4133 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 4028, 4030, 4035, 4039, 4053, 4056, 4062, 4067, 4070, 4073, 4076, 4078, 4079, 4082, 4084, 4089, 4093, 4098, 4101, 4105, 4116, 4118, 4123, 4127, 4130, 4132**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That

motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3, Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN

values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocusing (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2**

(**Equations 1 and 3**, respectively). Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4028 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4028MH0001520011403189C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4028MH0002650001403210R00		3210		MOTOR COUNT:		13935		RANGE (cm): 7.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4028MH0002650001403211S00		3211		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Dec-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4028		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4028	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4028MH0001520021403190C00	3190	13743	8.90	-0.3	0.2	38.2	0.8	255	1		
4028MH0001520021403191C00	3191	13791	8.45	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	223	2		
4028MH0001520021403192C00	3192	13839	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3		
4028MH0001520021403193C00	3193	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	159	4		
4028MH0001520021403194C00	3194	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	127	5		
4028MH0001520021403195C00	3195	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6		
4028MH0001520021403196C00	3196	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7		
4028MH0001520021403197C00	3197	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4028 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		first merge of: Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4028MH0001520011403199C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4028MH0002650001403208R00		3208		MOTOR COUNT:		13925		RANGE (cm): 7.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4028MH0002650001403209S00		3209		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Dec-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4028		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4028	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4028MH0001520021403200C00	3200	13733	8.99	-0.3	0.2	38.6	0.9	255	1		
4028MH0001520021403201C00	3201	13781	8.54	-0.2	0.2	37.0	0.8	223	2		
4028MH0001520021403202C00	3202	13829	8.12	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	191	3		
4028MH0001520021403203C00	3203	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4		
4028MH0001520021403204C00	3204	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	127	5		
4028MH0001520021403205C00	3205	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6		
4028MH0001520021403206C00	3206	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7		
4028MH0001520021403207C00	3207	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4028 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		second merge of: Sequoia2 drill cuttings – APXS spot 2 – ~55 mm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on sol 4032										
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4028MH0001520011403199C00						
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4033MH0001530001403260R00		3260		MOTOR COUNT:		13925		RANGE (cm): 7.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4033MH0001530001403261S00		3261		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Dec-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153		MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4028		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4033	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES		CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
					NEAR	FAR						
4028MH0001520021403200C00		3200	13733	8.99	-0.3	0.2	38.6	0.9	255	1		
4028MH0001520021403201C00		3201	13781	8.54	-0.2	0.2	37.0	0.8	223	2		
4028MH0001520021403202C00		3202	13829	8.12	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	191	3		
4028MH0001520021403203C00		3203	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4		
4028MH0001520021403204C00		3204	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	127	5		
4028MH0001520021403205C00		3205	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6		
4028MH0001520021403206C00		3206	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7		
4028MH0001520021403207C00		3207	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		first merge of: target Keeler_Needle - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4030MH0001680011403215C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4030MH0001930001403250R00	3250	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4030MH0001930001403251S00	3251	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4030	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4030		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4030MH0001680021403216C00	3216	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4030MH0001680021403217C00	3217	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4030MH0001680021403218C00	3218	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4030MH0001680021403219C00	3219	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4030MH0001680021403220C00	3220	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4030MH0001680021403221C00	3221	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4030MH0001680021403222C00	3222	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4030MH0001680021403223C00	3223	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		second merge of: target Keeler_Needle - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff - merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on sol 4032							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4030MH0001680011403215C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4033MH0001530001403258R00	3258	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4033MH0001530001403259S00	3259	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4030	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4033		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4030MH0001680021403216C00	3216	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4030MH0001680021403217C00	3217	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4030MH0001680021403218C00	3218	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4030MH0001680021403219C00	3219	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4030MH0001680021403220C00	3220	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4030MH0001680021403221C00	3221	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4030MH0001680021403222C00	3222	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4030MH0001680021403223C00	3223	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Keeler_Needle - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4030MH0001680011403225C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4030MH0001930001403248R00	3248	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4030MH0001930001403249S00	3249	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4030	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4030	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4030MH0001680021403226C00	3226	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4030MH0001680021403227C00	3227	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4030MH0001680021403228C00	3228	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4030MH0001680021403229C00	3229	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4030MH0001680021403230C00	3230	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4030MH0001680021403231C00	3231	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4030MH0001680021403232C00	3232	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4030MH0001680021403233C00	3233	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Keeler_Needle - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff - merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on sol 4032								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4030MH0001680011403225C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4033MH0001530001403256R00	3256	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4033MH0001530001403257S00	3257	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4030	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4033	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4030MH0001680021403226C00	3226	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4030MH0001680021403227C00	3227	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4030MH0001680021403228C00	3228	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4030MH0001680021403229C00	3229	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4030MH0001680021403230C00	3230	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4030MH0001680021403231C00	3231	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4030MH0001680021403232C00	3232	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4030MH0001680021403233C00	3233	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Keeler_Needle - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4030MH0001840011403235C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4030MH0001930001403246R00	3246	MOTOR COUNT:		14689	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4030MH0001930001403247S00	3247	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4030	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4030		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4030MH0001840021403236C00	3236	14545	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
4030MH0001840021403237C00	3237	14581	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2
4030MH0001840021403238C00	3238	14617	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3
4030MH0001840021403239C00	3239	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
4030MH0001840021403240C00	3240	14689	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
4030MH0001840021403241C00	3241	14725	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
4030MH0001840021403242C00	3242	14761	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
4030MH0001840021403243C00	3243	14797	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 11_December_2023

SOL 4030 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Keeler_Needle - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff - merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on sol 4032								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4030MH0001840011403235C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4033MH0001530001403254R00	3254	MOTOR COUNT:		14689	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4033MH0001530001403255S00	3255	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4030	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4033		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4030MH0001840021403236C00	3236	14545	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
4030MH0001840021403237C00	3237	14581	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2
4030MH0001840021403238C00	3238	14617	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3
4030MH0001840021403239C00	3239	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
4030MH0001840021403240C00	3240	14689	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
4030MH0001840021403241C00	3241	14725	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
4030MH0001840021403242C00	3242	14761	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
4030MH0001840021403243C00	3243	14797	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 14_December_2023

SOL 4035 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4035MH0001680011403265C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4035MH0001930001403298R00	3298	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4035MH0001930001403299S00	3299	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4035	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4035		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4035MH0001680021403266C00	3266	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4035MH0001680021403267C00	3267	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4035MH0001680021403268C00	3268	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4035MH0001680021403269C00	3269	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4035MH0001680021403270C00	3270	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4035MH0001680021403271C00	3271	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4035MH0001680021403272C00	3272	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4035MH0001680021403273C00	3273	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_December_2023

SOL 4035 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4035MH0001680011403275C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4035MH0001930001403296R00	3296	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4035MH0001930001403297S00	3297	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4035	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4035		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4035MH0001680021403276C00	3276	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
4035MH0001680021403277C00	3277	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4035MH0001680021403278C00	3278	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4035MH0001680021403279C00	3279	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4035MH0001680021403280C00	3280	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4035MH0001680021403281C00	3281	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4035MH0001680021403282C00	3282	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4035MH0001680021403283C00	3283	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_December_2023

SOL 4035 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wren_Peak – after sol 4032 DRT – ~2 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4035MH0003020011403285C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4035MH0001930001403294R00		3294		MOTOR COUNT:		14653		RANGE (cm):	3.9
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4035MH0001930001403295S00		3295		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Dec-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4035		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4035	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4035MH0003020021403286C00	3286	14533	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	255	1		
4035MH0003020021403287C00	3287	14563	4.21	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	223	2		
4035MH0003020021403288C00	3288	14593	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3		
4035MH0003020021403289C00	3289	14623	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	159	4		
4035MH0003020021403290C00	3290	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	127	5		
4035MH0003020021403291C00	3291	14683	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6		
4035MH0003020021403292C00	3292	14713	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7		
4035MH0003020021403293C00	3293	14743	3.66	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 19_December_2023

SOL 4039 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrow_Peak - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4039MH0001680011403309C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4040MH0002270001403374R00	3374	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4040MH0002270001403375S00	3375	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4039	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4040	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4039MH0001680021403310C00	3310	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4039MH0001680021403311C00	3311	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4039MH0001680021403312C00	3312	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4039MH0001680021403313C00	3313	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4039MH0001680021403314C00	3314	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4039MH0001680021403315C00	3315	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4039MH0001680021403316C00	3316	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4039MH0001680021403317C00	3317	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_December_2023

SOL 4039 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrow_Peak - after DRT - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4039MH0001680011403319C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4040MH0002270001403372R00	3372	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4040MH0002270001403373S00	3373	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Dec-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4039	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4040	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4039MH0001680021403320C00	3320	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4039MH0001680021403321C00	3321	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4039MH0001680021403322C00	3322	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4039MH0001680021403323C00	3323	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4039MH0001680021403324C00	3324	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4039MH0001680021403325C00	3325	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4039MH0001680021403326C00	3326	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4039MH0001680021403327C00	3327	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_December_2023

SOL 4039 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrow_Peak - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4039MH0007430011403335C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4040MH0002270001403370R00		3370		MOTOR COUNT:		14871		RANGE (cm): 3.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4040MH0002270001403371S00		3371		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		17-Dec-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4039		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4040	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4039MH0007430021403336C00	3336	14727	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	255	1		
4039MH0007430021403337C00	3337	14763	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	223	2		
4039MH0007430021403338C00	3338	14799	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	191	3		
4039MH0007430021403339C00	3339	14835	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	159	4		
4039MH0007430021403340C00	3340	14871	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	127	5		
4039MH0007430021403341C00	3341	14907	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	95	6		
4039MH0007430021403342C00	3342	14943	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	63	7		
4039MH0007430021403343C00	3343	14979	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 19_December_2023

SOL 4039 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4039MH0002970011403347C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4040MH0002270001403368R00		3368		MOTOR COUNT:		13996		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4040MH0002270001403369S00		3369		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		17-Dec-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4039		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4040	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4039MH0002970021403348C00	3348	13756	8.77	-0.2	0.2	37.8	0.8	255	1		
4039MH0002970021403349C00	3349	13816	8.23	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2		
4039MH0002970021403350C00	3350	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	191	3		
4039MH0002970021403351C00	3351	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4		
4039MH0002970021403352C00	3352	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5		
4039MH0002970021403353C00	3353	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6		
4039MH0002970021403354C00	3354	14116	6.14	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7		
4039MH0002970021403355C00	3355	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8		

UPDATED: 19_December_2023

SOL 4039 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4039MH0002970011403357C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4040MH0002270001403366R00	3366	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4040MH0002270001403367S00	3367	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Dec-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4039		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4040
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4039MH0002970021403358C00	3358	13755	8.78	-0.2	0.2	37.8	0.8	255	1
4039MH0002970021403359C00	3359	13815	8.24	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
4039MH0002970021403360C00	3360	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
4039MH0002970021403361C00	3361	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
4039MH0002970021403362C00	3362	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4039MH0002970021403363C00	3363	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4039MH0002970021403364C00	3364	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
4039MH0002970021403365C00	3365	14175	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 04_January_2024

SOL 4053 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Moose_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4053MH0001680011403379C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4054MH0001630001403478R00	3478	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4054MH0001630001403479S00	3479	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4053	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4054		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4053MH0001680021403380C00	3380	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4053MH0001680021403381C00	3381	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4053MH0001680021403382C00	3382	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4053MH0001680021403383C00	3383	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4053MH0001680021403384C00	3384	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4053MH0001680021403385C00	3385	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4053MH0001680021403386C00	3386	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4053MH0001680021403387C00	3387	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_January_2024

SOL 4053 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Moose_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4053MH0001680011403389C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4054MH0001630001403476R00	3476	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4054MH0001630001403477S00	3477	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4053	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4054		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4053MH0001680021403390C00	3390	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4053MH0001680021403391C00	3391	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4053MH0001680021403392C00	3392	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4053MH0001680021403393C00	3393	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4053MH0001680021403394C00	3394	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4053MH0001680021403395C00	3395	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4053MH0001680021403396C00	3396	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4053MH0001680021403397C00	3397	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_January_2024

SOL 4053 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Moose_Lake – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4053MH0007430011403399C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4054MH0001630001403474R00	3474	MOTOR COUNT:		15083	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4054MH0001630001403475S00	3475	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4053	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4054		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4053MH0007430021403400C00	3400	14939	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
4053MH0007430021403401C00	3401	14975	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
4053MH0007430021403402C00	3402	15011	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
4053MH0007430021403403C00	3403	15047	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
4053MH0007430021403404C00	3404	15083	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
4053MH0007430021403405C00	3405	15119	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4053MH0007430021403406C00	3406	15155	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
4053MH0007430021403407C00	3407	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 04_January_2024

SOL 4053 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lewis_Creek – stereo-1 – relief model position 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4053MH0001820011403411C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4054MH0001630001403472R00	3472	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4054MH0001630001403473S00	3473	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4053	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4054		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4053MH0001820021403412C00	3412	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
4053MH0001820021403413C00	3413	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4053MH0001820021403414C00	3414	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4053MH0001820021403415C00	3415	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4053MH0001820021403416C00	3416	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4053MH0001820021403417C00	3417	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4053MH0001820021403418C00	3418	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4053MH0001820021403419C00	3419	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_January_2024

SOL 4053 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lewis_Creek – stereo-2 – relief model position 2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4053MH0001820011403421C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4054MH0001630001403470R00	3470	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4054MH0001630001403471S00	3471	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4053	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4054	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4053MH0001820021403422C00	3422	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
4053MH0001820021403423C00	3423	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4053MH0001820021403424C00	3424	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4053MH0001820021403425C00	3425	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4053MH0001820021403426C00	3426	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4053MH0001820021403427C00	3427	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4053MH0001820021403428C00	3428	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4053MH0001820021403429C00	3429	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_January_2024

SOL 4053 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lewis_Creek – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4053MH0004260011403437C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4054MH0001630001403468R00	3468	MOTOR COUNT:		15060	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4054MH0001630001403469S00	3469	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00426	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Dec-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4053	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4054	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4053MH0004260021403438C00	3438	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1
4053MH0004260021403439C00	3439	14916	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	223	2
4053MH0004260021403440C00	3440	14964	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	191	3
4053MH0004260021403441C00	3441	15012	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	159	4
4053MH0004260021403442C00	3442	15060	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4053MH0004260021403443C00	3443	15108	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
4053MH0004260021403444C00	3444	15156	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
4053MH0004260021403445C00	3445	15204	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 08_January_2024

SOL 4056 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Green_Pass - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4056MH0001680011403483C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4057MH0001630001403559R00	3559	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4057MH0001630001403560S00	3560	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4056	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4057		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4056MH0001680021403484C00	3484	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4056MH0001680021403485C00	3485	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4056MH0001680021403486C00	3486	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4056MH0001680021403487C00	3487	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4056MH0001680021403488C00	3488	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4056MH0001680021403489C00	3489	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4056MH0001680021403490C00	3490	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4056MH0001680021403491C00	3491	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_January_2024

SOL 4056 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Green_Pass - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4056MH0001680011403493C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4057MH0001630001403557R00	3557	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4057MH0001630001403558S00	3558	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4056	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4057		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4056MH0001680021403494C00	3494	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4056MH0001680021403495C00	3495	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4056MH0001680021403496C00	3496	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4056MH0001680021403497C00	3497	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4056MH0001680021403498C00	3498	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4056MH0001680021403499C00	3499	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4056MH0001680021403500C00	3500	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4056MH0001680021403501C00	3501	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_January_2024

SOL 4056 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Green_Pass - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4056MH0007430011403503C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4057MH0001630001403555R00	3555	MOTOR COUNT:		15066	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4057MH0001630001403556S00	3556	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4056	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4057		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4056MH0007430021403504C00	3504	14922	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
4056MH0007430021403505C00	3505	14958	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	223	2
4056MH0007430021403506C00	3506	14994	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
4056MH0007430021403507C00	3507	15030	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
4056MH0007430021403508C00	3508	15066	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
4056MH0007430021403509C00	3509	15102	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	95	6
4056MH0007430021403510C00	3510	15138	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4056MH0007430021403511C00	3511	15174	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 08_January_2024

SOL 4056 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Wanda_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4056MH0001680011403515C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4057MH0001630001403553R00	3553	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4057MH0001630001403554S00	3554	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4056	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4057		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4056MH0001680021403516C00	3516	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
4056MH0001680021403517C00	3517	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4056MH0001680021403518C00	3518	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4056MH0001680021403519C00	3519	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4056MH0001680021403520C00	3520	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4056MH0001680021403521C00	3521	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4056MH0001680021403522C00	3522	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4056MH0001680021403523C00	3523	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_January_2024

SOL 4056 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Wanda_Lake – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4056MH0001680011403525C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4057MH0001630001403551R00	3551	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4057MH0001630001403552S00	3552	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4056	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4057	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4056MH0001680021403526C00	3526	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4056MH0001680021403527C00	3527	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4056MH0001680021403528C00	3528	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4056MH0001680021403529C00	3529	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4056MH0001680021403530C00	3530	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4056MH0001680021403531C00	3531	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4056MH0001680021403532C00	3532	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4056MH0001680021403533C00	3533	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_January_2024

SOL 4056 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Wanda_Lake – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4056MH0003020011403535C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4057MH0001630001403549R00	3549	MOTOR COUNT:		14648	RANGE (cm):	3.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4057MH0001630001403550S00	3550	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4056	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4057	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4056MH0003020021403536C00	3536	14528	4.32	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	255	1
4056MH0003020021403537C00	3537	14558	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	223	2
4056MH0003020021403538C00	3538	14588	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
4056MH0003020021403539C00	3539	14618	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	159	4
4056MH0003020021403540C00	3540	14648	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
4056MH0003020021403541C00	3541	14678	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6
4056MH0003020021403542C00	3542	14708	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7
4056MH0003020021403543C00	3543	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 11_January_2024

SOL 4062 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chagoopa - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4062MH0001680011403564C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4062MH0001930001403597R00	3597	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4062MH0001930001403598S00	3598	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4062	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4062	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4062MH0001680021403565C00	3565	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4062MH0001680021403566C00	3566	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4062MH0001680021403567C00	3567	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4062MH0001680021403568C00	3568	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4062MH0001680021403569C00	3569	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4062MH0001680021403570C00	3570	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4062MH0001680021403571C00	3571	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4062MH0001680021403572C00	3572	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_January_2024

SOL 4062 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chagoopa - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4062MH0001680011403574C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4062MH0001930001403595R00	3595	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4062MH0001930001403596S00	3596	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4062	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4062	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4062MH0001680021403575C00	3575	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4062MH0001680021403576C00	3576	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4062MH0001680021403577C00	3577	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4062MH0001680021403578C00	3578	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4062MH0001680021403579C00	3579	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4062MH0001680021403580C00	3580	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4062MH0001680021403581C00	3581	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4062MH0001680021403582C00	3582	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_January_2024

SOL 4062 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chagoopa – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4062MH0003020011403584C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4062MH0001930001403593R00	3593	MOTOR COUNT:		14711	RANGE (cm):		3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4062MH0001930001403594S00	3594	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jan-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4062		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4062
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4062MH0003020021403585C00	3585	14591	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	255	1
4062MH0003020021403586C00	3586	14621	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
4062MH0003020021403587C00	3587	14651	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	191	3
4062MH0003020021403588C00	3588	14681	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	159	4
4062MH0003020021403589C00	3589	14711	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
4062MH0003020021403590C00	3590	14741	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	95	6
4062MH0003020021403591C00	3591	14771	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
4062MH0003020021403592C00	3592	14801	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 18_January_2024

SOL 4067 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4067MH0002240011403602C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4068MH0001530001403649R00		3649		MOTOR COUNT:		13947		RANGE (cm):	7.2
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4068MH0001530001403650S00		3650		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4067		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4068	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4067MH0002240021403603C00	3603	13779	8.56	-0.2	0.2	37.0	0.8	255	1		
4067MH0002240021403604C00	3604	13821	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	223	2		
4067MH0002240021403605C00	3605	13863	7.84	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	191	3		
4067MH0002240021403606C00	3606	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4		
4067MH0002240021403607C00	3607	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	127	5		
4067MH0002240021403608C00	3608	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6		
4067MH0002240021403609C00	3609	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7		
4067MH0002240021403610C00	3610	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_January_2024

SOL 4067 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4067MH0002240011403612C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4068MH0001530001403647R00		3647		MOTOR COUNT:		13932		RANGE (cm):	7.3
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4068MH0001530001403648S00		3648		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4067		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4068	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4067MH0002240021403613C00	3613	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1		
4067MH0002240021403614C00	3614	13806	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2		
4067MH0002240021403615C00	3615	13848	7.96	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3		
4067MH0002240021403616C00	3616	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	159	4		
4067MH0002240021403617C00	3617	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	127	5		
4067MH0002240021403618C00	3618	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6		
4067MH0002240021403619C00	3619	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7		
4067MH0002240021403620C00	3620	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_January_2024

SOL 4067 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4067MH0002240011403622C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4068MH0001530001403645R00	3645	MOTOR COUNT:		13951	RANGE (cm):	7.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4068MH0001530001403646S00	3646	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4067	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4068		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4067MH0002240021403623C00	3623	13783	8.52	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	255	1
4067MH0002240021403624C00	3624	13825	8.15	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	223	2
4067MH0002240021403625C00	3625	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	191	3
4067MH0002240021403626C00	3626	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	159	4
4067MH0002240021403627C00	3627	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	127	5
4067MH0002240021403628C00	3628	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
4067MH0002240021403629C00	3629	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4067MH0002240021403630C00	3630	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 18_January_2024

SOL 4067 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4067MH0002240011403632C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4068MH0001530001403643R00	3643	MOTOR COUNT:		13936	RANGE (cm):	7.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4068MH0001530001403644S00	3644	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4067	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4068		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4067MH0002240021403633C00	3633	13768	8.66	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
4067MH0002240021403634C00	3634	13810	8.28	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	223	2
4067MH0002240021403635C00	3635	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	191	3
4067MH0002240021403636C00	3636	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	159	4
4067MH0002240021403637C00	3637	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	127	5
4067MH0002240021403638C00	3638	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
4067MH0002240021403639C00	3639	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4067MH0002240021403640C00	3640	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2024

SOL 4070 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Scheelite - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4070MH0001680011403654C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4071MH0001630001403725R00	3725	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4071MH0001630001403726S00	3726	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4070	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4071		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4070MH0001680021403655C00	3655	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4070MH0001680021403656C00	3656	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4070MH0001680021403657C00	3657	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4070MH0001680021403658C00	3658	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4070MH0001680021403659C00	3659	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4070MH0001680021403660C00	3660	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4070MH0001680021403661C00	3661	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4070MH0001680021403662C00	3662	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2024

SOL 4070 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Scheelite - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4070MH0001680011403664C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4071MH0001630001403723R00	3723	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4071MH0001630001403724S00	3724	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4070	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4071		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4070MH0001680021403665C00	3665	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4070MH0001680021403666C00	3666	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4070MH0001680021403667C00	3667	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4070MH0001680021403668C00	3668	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4070MH0001680021403669C00	3669	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4070MH0001680021403670C00	3670	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4070MH0001680021403671C00	3671	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4070MH0001680021403672C00	3672	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2024

SOL 4070 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Scheelite - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4070MH0007430011403674C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4071MH0001630001403721R00	3721	MOTOR COUNT:		15112	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4071MH0001630001403722S00	3722	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4070	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4071	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4070MH0007430021403675C00	3675	14968	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
4070MH0007430021403676C00	3676	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
4070MH0007430021403677C00	3677	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
4070MH0007430021403678C00	3678	15076	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
4070MH0007430021403679C00	3679	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4070MH0007430021403680C00	3680	15148	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4070MH0007430021403681C00	3681	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
4070MH0007430021403682C00	3682	15220	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2024

SOL 4070 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dorst - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4070MH0001820011403686C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4071MH0001630001403719R00	3719	MOTOR COUNT:		13981	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4071MH0001630001403720S00	3720	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4070	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4071	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4070MH0001820021403687C00	3687	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
4070MH0001820021403688C00	3688	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
4070MH0001820021403689C00	3689	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4070MH0001820021403690C00	3690	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4070MH0001820021403691C00	3691	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4070MH0001820021403692C00	3692	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4070MH0001820021403693C00	3693	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4070MH0001820021403694C00	3694	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2024

SOL 4070 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dorst - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4070MH0001820011403696C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4071MH0001630001403717R00	3717	MOTOR COUNT:		13986	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4071MH0001630001403718S00	3718	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4070	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4071		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4070MH0001820021403697C00	3697	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
4070MH0001820021403698C00	3698	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
4070MH0001820021403699C00	3699	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
4070MH0001820021403700C00	3700	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4070MH0001820021403701C00	3701	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4070MH0001820021403702C00	3702	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4070MH0001820021403703C00	3703	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4070MH0001820021403704C00	3704	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2024

SOL 4070 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dorst - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4070MH0003370011403706C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4071MH0001630001403715R00	3715	MOTOR COUNT:		14640	RANGE (cm):	4.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4071MH0001630001403716S00	3716	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00337	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4070	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4071		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4070MH0003370021403707C00	3707	14472	4.52	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	255	1
4070MH0003370021403708C00	3708	14514	4.37	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	223	2
4070MH0003370021403709C00	3709	14556	4.23	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	191	3
4070MH0003370021403710C00	3710	14598	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	159	4
4070MH0003370021403711C00	3711	14640	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
4070MH0003370021403712C00	3712	14682	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6
4070MH0003370021403713C00	3713	14724	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
4070MH0003370021403714C00	3714	14766	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4073 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mount_Langley - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4073MH0001680011403730C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4074MH0001630001403803R00	3803	MOTOR COUNT:		14048	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4074MH0001630001403804S00	3804	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4073	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4074	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4073MH0001680021403731C00	3731	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4073MH0001680021403732C00	3732	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4073MH0001680021403733C00	3733	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4073MH0001680021403734C00	3734	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4073MH0001680021403735C00	3735	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4073MH0001680021403736C00	3736	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4073MH0001680021403737C00	3737	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4073MH0001680021403738C00	3738	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4073 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mount_Langley - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4073MH0001680011403740C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4074MH0001630001403801R00	3801	MOTOR COUNT:		14050	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4074MH0001630001403802S00	3802	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4073	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4074	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4073MH0001680021403741C00	3741	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4073MH0001680021403742C00	3742	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4073MH0001680021403743C00	3743	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4073MH0001680021403744C00	3744	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4073MH0001680021403745C00	3745	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4073MH0001680021403746C00	3746	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4073MH0001680021403747C00	3747	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4073MH0001680021403748C00	3748	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4073 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mount_Langley - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4073MH0007430011403750C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4074MH0001630001403799R00	3799	MOTOR COUNT:		15251	RANGE (cm):	2.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4074MH0001630001403800S00	3800	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4073	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4074	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4073MH0007430021403751C00	3751	15107	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1
4073MH0007430021403752C00	3752	15143	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
4073MH0007430021403753C00	3753	15179	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
4073MH0007430021403754C00	3754	15215	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	159	4
4073MH0007430021403755C00	3755	15251	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	127	5
4073MH0007430021403756C00	3756	15287	2.50	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	95	6
4073MH0007430021403757C00	3757	15323	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
4073MH0007430021403758C00	3758	15359	2.38	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4073 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Sleeping_Beautys_Tower - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4073MH0001730011403764C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4074MH0001630001403797R00	3797	MOTOR COUNT:		13982	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4074MH0001630001403798S00	3798	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4073	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4074	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4073MH0001730021403765C00	3765	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
4073MH0001730021403766C00	3766	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
4073MH0001730021403767C00	3767	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
4073MH0001730021403768C00	3768	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
4073MH0001730021403769C00	3769	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4073MH0001730021403770C00	3770	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4073MH0001730021403771C00	3771	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
4073MH0001730021403772C00	3772	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4073 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sleeping_Beautys_Tower - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4073MH0001730011403774C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4074MH0001630001403795R00	3795	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4074MH0001630001403796S00	3796	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4073	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4074		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4073MH0001730021403775C00	3775	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
4073MH0001730021403776C00	3776	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
4073MH0001730021403777C00	3777	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
4073MH0001730021403778C00	3778	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4073MH0001730021403779C00	3779	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4073MH0001730021403780C00	3780	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4073MH0001730021403781C00	3781	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4073MH0001730021403782C00	3782	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4073 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sleeping_Beautys_Tower - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4073MH0003860011403784C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4074MH0001630001403793R00	3793	MOTOR COUNT:		15053	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4074MH0001630001403794S00	3794	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00386	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4073	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4074		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4073MH0003860021403785C00	3785	14837	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	255	1
4073MH0003860021403786C00	3786	14891	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	223	2
4073MH0003860021403787C00	3787	14945	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	191	3
4073MH0003860021403788C00	3788	14999	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4
4073MH0003860021403789C00	3789	15053	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4073MH0003860021403790C00	3790	15107	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
4073MH0003860021403791C00	3791	15161	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
4073MH0003860021403792C00	3792	15215	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 25_January_2024

SOL 4076 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Manzanita - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4076MH0001680011403808C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4076MH0001930001403841R00	3841	MOTOR COUNT:		14019	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4076MH0001930001403842S00	3842	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4076	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4076	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4076MH0001680021403809C00	3809	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4076MH0001680021403810C00	3810	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4076MH0001680021403811C00	3811	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4076MH0001680021403812C00	3812	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4076MH0001680021403813C00	3813	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4076MH0001680021403814C00	3814	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4076MH0001680021403815C00	3815	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4076MH0001680021403816C00	3816	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 25_January_2024

SOL 4076 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Manzanita - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4076MH0001680011403818C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4076MH0001930001403839R00	3839	MOTOR COUNT:		14021	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4076MH0001930001403840S00	3840	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4076	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4076	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4076MH0001680021403819C00	3819	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4076MH0001680021403820C00	3820	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4076MH0001680021403821C00	3821	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4076MH0001680021403822C00	3822	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4076MH0001680021403823C00	3823	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4076MH0001680021403824C00	3824	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4076MH0001680021403825C00	3825	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4076MH0001680021403826C00	3826	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 25_January_2024

SOL 4076 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Manzanita – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4076MH0003020011403828C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4076MH0001930001403837R00	3837	MOTOR COUNT:		14725	RANGE (cm):		3.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4076MH0001930001403838S00	3838	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Jan-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4076		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4076
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4076MH0003020021403829C00	3829	14605	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	255	1
4076MH0003020021403830C00	3830	14635	3.98	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	223	2
4076MH0003020021403831C00	3831	14665	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
4076MH0003020021403832C00	3832	14695	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	159	4
4076MH0003020021403833C00	3833	14725	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
4076MH0003020021403834C00	3834	14755	3.63	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	95	6
4076MH0003020021403835C00	3835	14785	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
4076MH0003020021403836C00	3836	14815	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4078 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sierra_Columbine - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4078MH0001820011403846C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4078MH0001930001403879R00	3879	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4078MH0001930001403880S00	3880	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4078	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4078	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4078MH0001820021403847C00	3847	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
4078MH0001820021403848C00	3848	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4078MH0001820021403849C00	3849	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4078MH0001820021403850C00	3850	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4078MH0001820021403851C00	3851	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4078MH0001820021403852C00	3852	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4078MH0001820021403853C00	3853	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4078MH0001820021403854C00	3854	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4078 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sierra_Columbine - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4078MH0001820011403856C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4078MH0001930001403877R00	3877	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4078MH0001930001403878S00	3878	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4078	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4078	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4078MH0001820021403857C00	3857	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
4078MH0001820021403858C00	3858	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4078MH0001820021403859C00	3859	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4078MH0001820021403860C00	3860	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4078MH0001820021403861C00	3861	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4078MH0001820021403862C00	3862	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4078MH0001820021403863C00	3863	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4078MH0001820021403864C00	3864	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2024

SOL 4078 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sierra_Columbine - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4078MH0007960011403866C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4078MH0001930001403875R00		3875		MOTOR COUNT:		15046		RANGE (cm): 2.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4078MH0001930001403876S00		3876		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		26-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4078		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL: 4078		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4078MH0007960021403867C00	3867	14878	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1		
4078MH0007960021403868C00	3868	14920	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2		
4078MH0007960021403869C00	3869	14962	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	191	3		
4078MH0007960021403870C00	3870	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4		
4078MH0007960021403871C00	3871	15046	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	127	5		
4078MH0007960021403872C00	3872	15088	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	95	6		
4078MH0007960021403873C00	3873	15130	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	63	7		
4078MH0007960021403874C00	3874	15172	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_February_2024

SOL 4079 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Simpson_Meadow - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4079MH0001680011403884C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4079MH0001630001403955R00	3955	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4079MH0001630001403956S00	3956	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4079	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4079	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4079MH0001680021403885C00	3885	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4079MH0001680021403886C00	3886	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4079MH0001680021403887C00	3887	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4079MH0001680021403888C00	3888	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4079MH0001680021403889C00	3889	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4079MH0001680021403890C00	3890	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4079MH0001680021403891C00	3891	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4079MH0001680021403892C00	3892	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_February_2024

SOL 4079 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Simpson_Meadow - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4079MH0001680011403894C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4079MH0001630001403953R00	3953	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4079MH0001630001403954S00	3954	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4079	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4079	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4079MH0001680021403895C00	3895	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4079MH0001680021403896C00	3896	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4079MH0001680021403897C00	3897	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4079MH0001680021403898C00	3898	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4079MH0001680021403899C00	3899	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4079MH0001680021403900C00	3900	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4079MH0001680021403901C00	3901	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4079MH0001680021403902C00	3902	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_February_2024

SOL 4079 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Simpson_Meadow – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4079MH0003020011403904C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4079MH0001630001403951R00	3951	MOTOR COUNT:		14697	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4079MH0001630001403952S00	3952	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4079	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4079	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4079MH0003020021403905C00	3905	14577	4.16	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	255	1
4079MH0003020021403906C00	3906	14607	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2
4079MH0003020021403907C00	3907	14637	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
4079MH0003020021403908C00	3908	14667	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
4079MH0003020021403909C00	3909	14697	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
4079MH0003020021403910C00	3910	14727	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
4079MH0003020021403911C00	3911	14757	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
4079MH0003020021403912C00	3912	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 12_February_2024

SOL 4079 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Sabrina – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4079MH0001680011403916C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4079MH0001630001403949R00	3949	MOTOR COUNT:		14025	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4079MH0001630001403950S00	3950	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4079	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4079	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4079MH0001680021403917C00	3917	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4079MH0001680021403918C00	3918	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4079MH0001680021403919C00	3919	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4079MH0001680021403920C00	3920	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4079MH0001680021403921C00	3921	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4079MH0001680021403922C00	3922	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4079MH0001680021403923C00	3923	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4079MH0001680021403924C00	3924	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_February_2024

SOL 4079 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Sabrina - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4079MH0001680011403926C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4079MH0001630001403947R00	3947	MOTOR COUNT:		14018	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4079MH0001630001403948S00	3948	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4079	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4079	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4079MH0001680021403927C00	3927	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4079MH0001680021403928C00	3928	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4079MH0001680021403929C00	3929	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4079MH0001680021403930C00	3930	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4079MH0001680021403931C00	3931	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4079MH0001680021403932C00	3932	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4079MH0001680021403933C00	3933	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4079MH0001680021403934C00	3934	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_February_2024

SOL 4079 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Sabrina - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4079MH0003020011403936C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4079MH0001630001403945R00	3945	MOTOR COUNT:		14743	RANGE (cm):	3.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4079MH0001630001403946S00	3946	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jan-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4079	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4079	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4079MH0003020021403937C00	3937	14623	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	255	1
4079MH0003020021403938C00	3938	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	223	2
4079MH0003020021403939C00	3939	14683	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	191	3
4079MH0003020021403940C00	3940	14713	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	159	4
4079MH0003020021403941C00	3941	14743	3.66	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	127	5
4079MH0003020021403942C00	3942	14773	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	95	6
4079MH0003020021403943C00	3943	14803	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	63	7
4079MH0003020021403944C00	3944	14833	3.43	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 04_March_2024

SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target June_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0001680011403964C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4083MH0001700001404061R00		4061		MOTOR COUNT:		13998		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404062S00		4062		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		30-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4082MH0001680021403965C00	3965	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1		
4082MH0001680021403966C00	3966	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2		
4082MH0001680021403967C00	3967	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3		
4082MH0001680021403968C00	3968	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4		
4082MH0001680021403969C00	3969	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5		
4082MH0001680021403970C00	3970	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
4082MH0001680021403971C00	3971	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7		
4082MH0001680021403972C00	3972	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 04_March_2024

SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target June_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0001680011403974C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4083MH0001700001404059R00		4059		MOTOR COUNT:		14000		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404060S00		4060		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		30-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4082MH0001680021403975C00	3975	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1		
4082MH0001680021403976C00	3976	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2		
4082MH0001680021403977C00	3977	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3		
4082MH0001680021403978C00	3978	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
4082MH0001680021403979C00	3979	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5		
4082MH0001680021403980C00	3980	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
4082MH0001680021403981C00	3981	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7		
4082MH0001680021403982C00	3982	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target June_Lake - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0003020011403984C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4083MH0001700001404057R00		4057		MOTOR COUNT:		14679		RANGE (cm): 3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404058S00		4058		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		30-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4082MH0003020021403985C00	3985	14559	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	255	1		
4082MH0003020021403986C00	3986	14589	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	223	2		
4082MH0003020021403987C00	3987	14619	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3		
4082MH0003020021403988C00	3988	14649	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4		
4082MH0003020021403989C00	3989	14679	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	127	5		
4082MH0003020021403990C00	3990	14709	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	95	6		
4082MH0003020021403991C00	3991	14739	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	63	7		
4082MH0003020021403992C00	3992	14769	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	31	8		

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SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0008410011403996C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4083MH0001700001404055R00		4055		MOTOR COUNT:		13309		RANGE (cm): 15.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404056S00		4056		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00841		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		30-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4082MH0008410021403997C00	3997	13237	17.34	-0.8	0.8	67.9	2.9	255	1		
4082MH0008410021403998C00	3998	13255	16.84	-0.8	0.8	66.2	2.7	223	2		
4082MH0008410021403999C00	3999	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	191	3		
4082MH0008410021404000C00	4000	13291	15.90	-0.7	0.7	62.9	2.4	159	4		
4082MH0008410021404001C00	4001	13309	15.47	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	127	5		
4082MH0008410021404002C00	4002	13327	15.05	-0.6	0.6	59.9	2.2	95	6		
4082MH0008410021404003C00	4003	13345	14.66	-0.6	0.6	58.5	2.1	63	7		
4082MH0008410021404004C00	4004	13363	14.28	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	31	8		

UPDATED: 04_March_2024

SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0008410011404006C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4083MH0001700001404053R00		4053		MOTOR COUNT:		13307		RANGE (cm):	15.5
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404054S00		4054		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00841		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		30-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4082MH0008410021404007C00	4007	13235	17.40	-0.8	0.8	68.1	2.9	255	1		
4082MH0008410021404008C00	4008	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	223	2		
4082MH0008410021404009C00	4009	13271	16.41	-0.7	0.7	64.7	2.6	191	3		
4082MH0008410021404010C00	4010	13289	15.95	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	159	4		
4082MH0008410021404011C00	4011	13307	15.52	-0.7	0.7	61.5	2.3	127	5		
4082MH0008410021404012C00	4012	13325	15.10	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	95	6		
4082MH0008410021404013C00	4013	13343	14.70	-0.6	0.6	58.6	2.1	63	7		
4082MH0008410021404014C00	4014	13361	14.32	-0.6	0.6	57.3	2.0	31	8		

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SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Martha_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0003360011404018C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4083MH0001700001404051R00		4051		MOTOR COUNT:		13997		RANGE (cm):	6.9
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4083MH0001700001404052S00		4052		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		30-Jan-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4082MH0003360021404019C00	4019	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1		
4082MH0003360021404020C00	4020	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2		
4082MH0003360021404021C00	4021	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3		
4082MH0003360021404022C00	4022	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4		
4082MH0003360021404023C00	4023	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5		
4082MH0003360021404024C00	4024	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6		
4082MH0003360021404025C00	4025	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7		
4082MH0003360021404026C00	4026	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8		

UPDATED: 04_March_2024

SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Martha_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0003360011404028C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4083MH0001700001404049R00	4049	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4083MH0001700001404050S00	4050	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4082MH0003360021404029C00	4029	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4082MH0003360021404030C00	4030	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4082MH0003360021404031C00	4031	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4082MH0003360021404032C00	4032	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4082MH0003360021404033C00	4033	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4082MH0003360021404034C00	4034	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4082MH0003360021404035C00	4035	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4082MH0003360021404036C00	4036	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4082 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Martha_Lake - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4082MH0008480011404038C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4083MH0001700001404047R00	4047	MOTOR COUNT:		15096	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4083MH0001700001404048S00	4048	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Jan-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4082	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4083	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4082MH0008480021404039C00	4039	15000	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
4082MH0008480021404040C00	4040	15024	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
4082MH0008480021404041C00	4041	15048	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
4082MH0008480021404042C00	4042	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
4082MH0008480021404043C00	4043	15096	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
4082MH0008480021404044C00	4044	15120	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4082MH0008480021404045C00	4045	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4082MH0008480021404046C00	4046	15168	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 28_February_2024

SOL 4084 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grizzly_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4084MH0001680011404066C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4084MH0001930001404099R00	4099	MOTOR COUNT:	14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4084MH0001930001404100S00	4100	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4084	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4084		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4084MH0001680021404067C00	4067	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4084MH0001680021404068C00	4068	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4084MH0001680021404069C00	4069	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4084MH0001680021404070C00	4070	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4084MH0001680021404071C00	4071	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4084MH0001680021404072C00	4072	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4084MH0001680021404073C00	4073	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4084MH0001680021404074C00	4074	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_February_2024

SOL 4084 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grizzly_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4084MH0001680011404076C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4084MH0001930001404097R00	4097	MOTOR COUNT:	14036	RANGE (cm):	6.6			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4084MH0001930001404098S00	4098	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4084	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4084		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4084MH0001680021404077C00	4077	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4084MH0001680021404078C00	4078	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4084MH0001680021404079C00	4079	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4084MH0001680021404080C00	4080	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4084MH0001680021404081C00	4081	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
4084MH0001680021404082C00	4082	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4084MH0001680021404083C00	4083	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4084MH0001680021404084C00	4084	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4084 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grizzly_Lake – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4084MH0007430011404086C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4084MH0001930001404095R00		4095		MOTOR COUNT:		15219	RANGE (cm):	2.6
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4084MH0001930001404096S00		4096		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Feb-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4084		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4084
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4084MH0007430021404087C00	4087	15075	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1	
4084MH0007430021404088C00	4088	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2	
4084MH0007430021404089C00	4089	15147	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	191	3	
4084MH0007430021404090C00	4090	15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4	
4084MH0007430021404091C00	4091	15219	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5	
4084MH0007430021404092C00	4092	15255	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	95	6	
4084MH0007430021404093C00	4093	15291	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7	
4084MH0007430021404094C00	4094	15327	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8	

UPDATED: 28_February_2024

SOL 4089 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4089MH0001820011404124C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4089MH0002650001404147R00	4147	MOTOR COUNT:		14013	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4089MH0002650001404148S00	4148	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4089	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4089		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4089MH0001820021404125C00	4125	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4089MH0001820021404126C00	4126	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4089MH0001820021404127C00	4127	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4089MH0001820021404128C00	4128	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4089MH0001820021404129C00	4129	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4089MH0001820021404130C00	4130	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4089MH0001820021404131C00	4131	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4089MH0001820021404132C00	4132	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4089 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4089MH0001820011404134C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4089MH0002650001404145R00	4145	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4089MH0002650001404146S00	4146	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4089	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4089		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4089MH0001820021404135C00	4135	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4089MH0001820021404136C00	4136	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4089MH0001820021404137C00	4137	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4089MH0001820021404138C00	4138	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4089MH0001820021404139C00	4139	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4089MH0001820021404140C00	4140	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4089MH0001820021404141C00	4141	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4089MH0001820021404142C00	4142	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4093 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4093MH0001820011404152C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4093MH0002270001404229R00	4229	MOTOR COUNT:		14039	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4093MH0002270001404230S00	4230	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4093	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4093	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4093MH0001820021404153C00	4153	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4093MH0001820021404154C00	4154	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4093MH0001820021404155C00	4155	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4093MH0001820021404156C00	4156	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4093MH0001820021404157C00	4157	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4093MH0001820021404158C00	4158	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4093MH0001820021404159C00	4159	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4093MH0001820021404160C00	4160	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_February_2024

SOL 4093 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4093MH0001820011404162C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4093MH0002270001404227R00	4227	MOTOR COUNT:		14045	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4093MH0002270001404228S00	4228	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4093	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4093	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4093MH0001820021404163C00	4163	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4093MH0001820021404164C00	4164	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4093MH0001820021404165C00	4165	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4093MH0001820021404166C00	4166	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4093MH0001820021404167C00	4167	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4093MH0001820021404168C00	4168	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4093MH0001820021404169C00	4169	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4093MH0001820021404170C00	4170	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4093 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Miter – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4093MH0001680011404192C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4093MH0002270001404225R00	4225	MOTOR COUNT:		13957	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4093MH0002270001404226S00	4226	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4093	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4093		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4093MH0001680021404193C00	4193	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
4093MH0001680021404194C00	4194	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
4093MH0001680021404195C00	4195	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
4093MH0001680021404196C00	4196	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
4093MH0001680021404197C00	4197	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
4093MH0001680021404198C00	4198	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6
4093MH0001680021404199C00	4199	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	63	7
4093MH0001680021404200C00	4200	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4093 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Miter – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4093MH0001680011404202C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4093MH0002270001404223R00	4223	MOTOR COUNT:		13968	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4093MH0002270001404224S00	4224	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4093	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4093		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4093MH0001680021404203C00	4203	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4093MH0001680021404204C00	4204	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
4093MH0001680021404205C00	4205	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4093MH0001680021404206C00	4206	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
4093MH0001680021404207C00	4207	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
4093MH0001680021404208C00	4208	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
4093MH0001680021404209C00	4209	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4093MH0001680021404210C00	4210	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4093 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Miter – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4093MH0003020011404212C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4093MH0002270001404221R00	4221	MOTOR COUNT:		14589	RANGE (cm):		4.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4093MH0002270001404222S00	4222	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4093	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4093	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4093MH0003020021404213C00	4213	14469	4.53	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	255	1
4093MH0003020021404214C00	4214	14499	4.43	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	223	2
4093MH0003020021404215C00	4215	14529	4.32	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	191	3
4093MH0003020021404216C00	4216	14559	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	159	4
4093MH0003020021404217C00	4217	14589	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	127	5
4093MH0003020021404218C00	4218	14619	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	95	6
4093MH0003020021404219C00	4219	14649	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	63	7
4093MH0003020021404220C00	4220	14679	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 28_February_2024

SOL 4098 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Horseshoe_Meadows - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4098MH0001680011404234C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4098MH0001930001404279R00	4279	MOTOR COUNT:		14010	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4098MH0001930001404280S00	4280	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4098	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4098	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4098MH0001680021404235C00	4235	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4098MH0001680021404236C00	4236	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4098MH0001680021404237C00	4237	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4098MH0001680021404238C00	4238	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4098MH0001680021404239C00	4239	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4098MH0001680021404240C00	4240	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4098MH0001680021404241C00	4241	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4098MH0001680021404242C00	4242	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_February_2024

SOL 4098 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Horseshoe_Meadows - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4098MH0001680011404244C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4098MH0001930001404277R00	4277	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4098MH0001930001404278S00	4278	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4098	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4098	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4098MH0001680021404245C00	4245	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4098MH0001680021404246C00	4246	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4098MH0001680021404247C00	4247	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4098MH0001680021404248C00	4248	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4098MH0001680021404249C00	4249	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4098MH0001680021404250C00	4250	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4098MH0001680021404251C00	4251	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4098MH0001680021404252C00	4252	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4098 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Horseshoe_Meadows – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4098MH0007430011404254C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4098MH0001930001404275R00		4275		MOTOR COUNT:		15122		RANGE (cm):	2.8
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4098MH0001930001404276S00		4276		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Feb-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4098		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4098	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4098MH0007430021404255C00	4255	14978	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1		
4098MH0007430021404256C00	4256	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2		
4098MH0007430021404257C00	4257	15050	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3		
4098MH0007430021404258C00	4258	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4		
4098MH0007430021404259C00	4259	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5		
4098MH0007430021404260C00	4260	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6		
4098MH0007430021404261C00	4261	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7		
4098MH0007430021404262C00	4262	15230	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 08_March_2024

SOL 4101 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4101MH0001820011404286C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4102MH0001530001404333R00	4333	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4102MH0001530001404334S00	4334	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4101	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4102	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4101MH0001820021404287C00	4287	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4101MH0001820021404288C00	4288	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4101MH0001820021404289C00	4289	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
4101MH0001820021404290C00	4290	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4101MH0001820021404291C00	4291	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4101MH0001820021404292C00	4292	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4101MH0001820021404293C00	4293	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4101MH0001820021404294C00	4294	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_March_2024

SOL 4101 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4101MH0001820011404296C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4102MH0001530001404331R00	4331	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4102MH0001530001404332S00	4332	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4101	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4102	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4101MH0001820021404297C00	4297	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4101MH0001820021404298C00	4298	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
4101MH0001820021404299C00	4299	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4101MH0001820021404300C00	4300	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4101MH0001820021404301C00	4301	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4101MH0001820021404302C00	4302	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4101MH0001820021404303C00	4303	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4101MH0001820021404304C00	4304	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_March_2024

SOL 4101 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4101MH0001820011404308C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4102MH0001530001404329R00	4329	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4102MH0001530001404330S00	4330	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4101	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4102	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4101MH0001820021404309C00	4309	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4101MH0001820021404310C00	4310	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4101MH0001820021404311C00	4311	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4101MH0001820021404312C00	4312	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4101MH0001820021404313C00	4313	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4101MH0001820021404314C00	4314	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4101MH0001820021404315C00	4315	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4101MH0001820021404316C00	4316	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_March_2024

SOL 4101 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4101MH0001820011404318C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4102MH0001530001404327R00	4327	MOTOR COUNT:		14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4102MH0001530001404328S00	4328	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4101	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4102	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4101MH0001820021404319C00	4319	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4101MH0001820021404320C00	4320	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4101MH0001820021404321C00	4321	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4101MH0001820021404322C00	4322	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4101MH0001820021404323C00	4323	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4101MH0001820021404324C00	4324	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4101MH0001820021404325C00	4325	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4101MH0001820021404326C00	4326	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 1 of 7 - ~30 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404336C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4106MH0004490001404469R00		4469		MOTOR COUNT:		12943		RANGE (cm): 31.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4106MH0004490001404470S00		4470		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-Feb-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4105MH0008740021404337C00	4337	12823	46.37	-5.1	6.6	170.1	20.7	255	1		
4105MH0008740021404338C00	4338	12853	41.70	-4.2	5.3	153.7	16.7	223	2		
4105MH0008740021404339C00	4339	12883	37.84	-3.5	4.3	140.1	13.6	191	3		
4105MH0008740021404340C00	4340	12913	34.60	-3.0	3.5	128.7	11.4	159	4		
4105MH0008740021404341C00	4341	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	127	5		
4105MH0008740021404342C00	4342	12973	29.47	-2.2	2.5	110.6	8.2	95	6		
4105MH0008740021404343C00	4343	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	63	7		
4105MH0008740021404344C00	4344	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 2 of 7 - ~30 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404346C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4106MH0004490001404467R00		4467		MOTOR COUNT:		12942		RANGE (cm): 31.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4106MH0004490001404468S00		4468		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-Feb-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4105MH0008740021404347C00	4347	12822	46.55	-5.2	6.7	170.7	20.9	255	1		
4105MH0008740021404348C00	4348	12852	41.84	-4.2	5.3	154.2	16.8	223	2		
4105MH0008740021404349C00	4349	12882	37.96	-3.5	4.3	140.5	13.7	191	3		
4105MH0008740021404350C00	4350	12912	34.70	-3.0	3.5	129.1	11.4	159	4		
4105MH0008740021404351C00	4351	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	127	5		
4105MH0008740021404352C00	4352	12972	29.54	-2.2	2.5	110.9	8.3	95	6		
4105MH0008740021404353C00	4353	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	63	7		
4105MH0008740021404354C00	4354	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 3 of 7 - ~29 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404356C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404465R00	4465	MOTOR COUNT:		12951	RANGE (cm):	31.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404466S00	4466	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0008740021404357C00	4357	12831	45.03	-4.9	6.2	165.4	19.5	255	1
4105MH0008740021404358C00	4358	12861	40.60	-4.0	5.0	149.8	15.8	223	2
4105MH0008740021404359C00	4359	12891	36.92	-3.3	4.0	136.9	13.0	191	3
4105MH0008740021404360C00	4360	12921	33.82	-2.8	3.4	126.0	10.9	159	4
4105MH0008740021404361C00	4361	12951	31.18	-2.4	2.8	116.6	9.2	127	5
4105MH0008740021404362C00	4362	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	95	6
4105MH0008740021404363C00	4363	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	63	7
4105MH0008740021404364C00	4364	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 4 of 7 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404366C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404463R00	4463	MOTOR COUNT:		12970	RANGE (cm):	29.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404464S00	4464	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0008740021404367C00	4367	12850	42.12	-4.3	5.4	155.2	17.0	255	1
4105MH0008740021404368C00	4368	12880	38.19	-3.6	4.4	141.4	13.9	223	2
4105MH0008740021404369C00	4369	12910	34.90	-3.0	3.6	129.8	11.6	191	3
4105MH0008740021404370C00	4370	12940	32.10	-2.6	3.0	119.9	9.8	159	4
4105MH0008740021404371C00	4371	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	127	5
4105MH0008740021404372C00	4372	13000	27.59	-1.9	2.2	104.0	7.2	95	6
4105MH0008740021404373C00	4373	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	63	7
4105MH0008740021404374C00	4374	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 5 of 7 - ~27 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404376C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404461R00			4461	MOTOR COUNT:		12979	RANGE (cm):	29.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404462S00			4462	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4105		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0008740021404377C00	4377	12859	40.87	-4.1	5.0	150.8	16.0	255	1
4105MH0008740021404378C00	4378	12889	37.15	-3.4	4.1	137.7	13.2	223	2
4105MH0008740021404379C00	4379	12919	34.02	-2.9	3.4	126.6	11.0	191	3
4105MH0008740021404380C00	4380	12949	31.34	-2.4	2.9	117.2	9.3	159	4
4105MH0008740021404381C00	4381	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	127	5
4105MH0008740021404382C00	4382	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	95	6
4105MH0008740021404383C00	4383	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	63	7
4105MH0008740021404384C00	4384	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 6 of 7 - ~42 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404386C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404459R00			4459	MOTOR COUNT:		12837	RANGE (cm):	44.1
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404460S00			4460	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4105		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0008740021404387C00	4387	12717	75.63	-12.8	19.8	273.1	57.4	255	1
4105MH0008740021404388C00	4388	12747	64.30	-9.5	13.7	233.2	40.8	223	2
4105MH0008740021404389C00	4389	12777	55.84	-7.3	10.0	203.5	30.4	191	3
4105MH0008740021404390C00	4390	12807	49.30	-5.8	7.6	180.4	23.5	159	4
4105MH0008740021404391C00	4391	12837	44.07	-4.7	5.9	162.0	18.7	127	5
4105MH0008740021404392C00	4392	12867	39.81	-3.9	4.8	147.0	15.1	95	6
4105MH0008740021404393C00	4393	12897	36.26	-3.2	3.9	134.5	12.5	63	7
4105MH0008740021404394C00	4394	12927	33.26	-2.7	3.2	124.0	10.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 7 of 7 - standoff beyond 50 cm - images do not have in-focus elements								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008740011404396C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404457R00	4457	MOTOR COUNT:		13416	RANGE (cm):	13.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404458S00	4458	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00874	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0008740021404397C00	4397	13296	15.78	-0.7	0.7	62.4	2.4	255	1
4105MH0008740021404398C00	4398	13326	15.08	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	223	2
4105MH0008740021404399C00	4399	13356	14.42	-0.6	0.6	57.7	2.0	191	3
4105MH0008740021404400C00	4400	13386	13.82	-0.5	0.5	55.5	1.9	159	4
4105MH0008740021404401C00	4401	13416	13.25	-0.5	0.5	53.5	1.7	127	5
4105MH0008740021404402C00	4402	13446	12.72	-0.5	0.5	51.7	1.6	95	6
4105MH0008740021404403C00	4403	13476	12.22	-0.4	0.4	49.9	1.5	63	7
4105MH0008740021404404C00	4404	13506	11.76	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mineral_King - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0003360011404408C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404455R00	4455	MOTOR COUNT:		14012	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404456S00	4456	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0003360021404409C00	4409	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4105MH0003360021404410C00	4410	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4105MH0003360021404411C00	4411	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4105MH0003360021404412C00	4412	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4105MH0003360021404413C00	4413	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4105MH0003360021404414C00	4414	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4105MH0003360021404415C00	4415	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4105MH0003360021404416C00	4416	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0003360011404418C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404453R00	4453	MOTOR COUNT:		14024	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404454S00	4454	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0003360021404419C00	4419	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4105MH0003360021404420C00	4420	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4105MH0003360021404421C00	4421	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4105MH0003360021404422C00	4422	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4105MH0003360021404423C00	4423	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4105MH0003360021404424C00	4424	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4105MH0003360021404425C00	4425	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4105MH0003360021404426C00	4426	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0008730011404428C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404451R00	4451	MOTOR COUNT:		14723	RANGE (cm):	3.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404452S00	4452	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00873	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0008730021404429C00	4429	14627	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	255	1
4105MH0008730021404430C00	4430	14651	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	223	2
4105MH0008730021404431C00	4431	14675	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	191	3
4105MH0008730021404432C00	4432	14699	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	159	4
4105MH0008730021404433C00	4433	14723	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
4105MH0008730021404434C00	4434	14747	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	95	6
4105MH0008730021404435C00	4435	14771	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
4105MH0008730021404436C00	4436	14795	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4105 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4105MH0003360011404438C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4106MH0004490001404449R00	4449	MOTOR COUNT:		14010	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4106MH0004490001404450S00	4450	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4105	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4106	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4105MH0003360021404439C00	4439	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4105MH0003360021404440C00	4440	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4105MH0003360021404441C00	4441	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4105MH0003360021404442C00	4442	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4105MH0003360021404443C00	4443	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4105MH0003360021404444C00	4444	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4105MH0003360021404445C00	4445	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4105MH0003360021404446C00	4446	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4116 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4116MH0001520011404476C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4116MH0002650001404497R00	4497	MOTOR COUNT:		14177	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4116MH0002650001404498S00	4498	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4116	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4116		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4116MH0001520021404477C00	4477	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4116MH0001520021404478C00	4478	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	223	2
4116MH0001520021404479C00	4479	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	191	3
4116MH0001520021404480C00	4480	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	159	4
4116MH0001520021404481C00	4481	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	127	5
4116MH0001520021404482C00	4482	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6
4116MH0001520021404483C00	4483	14273	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
4116MH0001520021404484C00	4484	14321	5.13	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4116 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4116MH0001520011404486C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4116MH0002650001404495R00	4495	MOTOR COUNT:		14160	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4116MH0002650001404496S00	4496	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4116	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4116		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4116MH0001520021404487C00	4487	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4116MH0001520021404488C00	4488	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
4116MH0001520021404489C00	4489	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3
4116MH0001520021404490C00	4490	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
4116MH0001520021404491C00	4491	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4116MH0001520021404492C00	4492	14208	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
4116MH0001520021404493C00	4493	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
4116MH0001520021404494C00	4494	14304	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4118 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mineral_King2 - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4118MH0001680011404511C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4118MH0001530001404558R00	4558	MOTOR COUNT:		14011	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4118MH0001530001404559S00	4559	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4118	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4118		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4118MH0001680021404512C00	4512	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4118MH0001680021404513C00	4513	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4118MH0001680021404514C00	4514	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4118MH0001680021404515C00	4515	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4118MH0001680021404516C00	4516	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4118MH0001680021404517C00	4517	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4118MH0001680021404518C00	4518	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4118MH0001680021404519C00	4519	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4118 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mineral_King2 - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4118MH0001680011404521C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4118MH0001530001404556R00	4556	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4118MH0001530001404557S00	4557	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4118	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4118		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4118MH0001680021404522C00	4522	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4118MH0001680021404523C00	4523	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4118MH0001680021404524C00	4524	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4118MH0001680021404525C00	4525	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4118MH0001680021404526C00	4526	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4118MH0001680021404527C00	4527	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4118MH0001680021404528C00	4528	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4118MH0001680021404529C00	4529	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4118 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King2 - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4118MH0003020011404531C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4118MH0001530001404554R00	4554	MOTOR COUNT:		14711	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4118MH0001530001404555S00	4555	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4118	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4118	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4118MH0003020021404532C00	4532	14591	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	255	1
4118MH0003020021404533C00	4533	14621	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
4118MH0003020021404534C00	4534	14651	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	191	3
4118MH0003020021404535C00	4535	14681	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	159	4
4118MH0003020021404536C00	4536	14711	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
4118MH0003020021404537C00	4537	14741	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	95	6
4118MH0003020021404538C00	4538	14771	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
4118MH0003020021404539C00	4539	14801	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 11_March_2024

SOL 4118 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King2 - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4118MH0001680011404541C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4118MH0001530001404552R00	4552	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4118MH0001530001404553S00	4553	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4118	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4118	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4118MH0001680021404542C00	4542	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4118MH0001680021404543C00	4543	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4118MH0001680021404544C00	4544	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4118MH0001680021404545C00	4545	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4118MH0001680021404546C00	4546	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4118MH0001680021404547C00	4547	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4118MH0001680021404548C00	4548	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4118MH0001680021404549C00	4549	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_March_2024

SOL 4123 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King3 - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4123MH0001680011404563C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4123MH0001530001404610R00	4610	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4123MH0001530001404611S00	4611	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4123	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4123	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4123MH0001680021404564C00	4564	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4123MH0001680021404565C00	4565	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4123MH0001680021404566C00	4566	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4123MH0001680021404567C00	4567	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4123MH0001680021404568C00	4568	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4123MH0001680021404569C00	4569	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4123MH0001680021404570C00	4570	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4123MH0001680021404571C00	4571	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_March_2024

SOL 4123 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King3 - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4123MH0001680011404573C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4123MH0001530001404608R00	4608	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4123MH0001530001404609S00	4609	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4123	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4123	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4123MH0001680021404574C00	4574	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4123MH0001680021404575C00	4575	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4123MH0001680021404576C00	4576	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4123MH0001680021404577C00	4577	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4123MH0001680021404578C00	4578	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4123MH0001680021404579C00	4579	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4123MH0001680021404580C00	4580	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4123MH0001680021404581C00	4581	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_March_2024

SOL 4123 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mineral_King3 - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4123MH0007430011404583C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4123MH0001530001404606R00	4606	MOTOR COUNT:		15113	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4123MH0001530001404607S00	4607	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4123	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4123		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4123MH0007430021404584C00	4584	14969	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
4123MH0007430021404585C00	4585	15005	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
4123MH0007430021404586C00	4586	15041	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
4123MH0007430021404587C00	4587	15077	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
4123MH0007430021404588C00	4588	15113	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4123MH0007430021404589C00	4589	15149	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
4123MH0007430021404590C00	4590	15185	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
4123MH0007430021404591C00	4591	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_March_2024

SOL 4123 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mineral_King3 - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4123MH0001680011404593C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4123MH0001530001404604R00	4604	MOTOR COUNT:		13978	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4123MH0001530001404605S00	4605	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4123	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4123		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4123MH0001680021404594C00	4594	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4123MH0001680021404595C00	4595	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4123MH0001680021404596C00	4596	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4123MH0001680021404597C00	4597	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4123MH0001680021404598C00	4598	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4123MH0001680021404599C00	4599	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4123MH0001680021404600C00	4600	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4123MH0001680021404601C00	4601	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_March_2024

SOL 4127 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - ~4 cm standoff										
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4127MH0002990011404617C00						
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4128MH0002580001404628R00		4628		MOTOR COUNT:		14150		RANGE (cm): 6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4128MH0002580001404629S00		4629		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		16-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00258		MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4127		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4128	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8			
				NEAR	FAR							
4127MH0002990021404618C00	4618	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1			
4127MH0002990021404619C00	4619	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	223	2			
4127MH0002990021404620C00	4620	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	191	3			
4127MH0002990021404621C00	4621	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4			
4127MH0002990021404622C00	4622	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	127	5			
4127MH0002990021404623C00	4623	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	95	6			
4127MH0002990021404624C00	4624	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7			
4127MH0002990021404625C00	4625	14258	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	31	8			

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SOL 4130 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tunnel_View - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4130MH0001680011404633C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4130MH0002270001304690R00	4690	MOTOR COUNT:		14046	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4130MH0002270001304691S00	4691	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4130	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4130	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4130MH0001680021404634C00	4634	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4130MH0001680021404635C00	4635	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4130MH0001680021404636C00	4636	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4130MH0001680021404637C00	4637	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4130MH0001680021404638C00	4638	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4130MH0001680021404639C00	4639	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4130MH0001680021404640C00	4640	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4130MH0001680021404641C00	4641	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4130 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tunnel_View - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4130MH0001680011404643C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4130MH0002270001304688R00	4688	MOTOR COUNT:		14055	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4130MH0002270001304689S00	4689	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4130	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4130	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4130MH0001680021404644C00	4644	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4130MH0001680021404645C00	4645	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4130MH0001680021404646C00	4646	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4130MH0001680021404647C00	4647	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
4130MH0001680021404648C00	4648	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4130MH0001680021404649C00	4649	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
4130MH0001680021404650C00	4650	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4130MH0001680021404651C00	4651	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4130 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tunnel_View - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4130MH0007430011404653C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4130MH0002270001304686R00		4686		MOTOR COUNT:		15264		RANGE (cm): 2.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304687S00		4687		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		19-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4130		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4130	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4130MH0007430021404654C00	4654	15120	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	255	1		
4130MH0007430021404655C00	4655	15156	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	223	2		
4130MH0007430021404656C00	4656	15192	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	191	3		
4130MH0007430021404657C00	4657	15228	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	159	4		
4130MH0007430021404658C00	4658	15264	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	127	5		
4130MH0007430021404659C00	4659	15300	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	95	6		
4130MH0007430021404660C00	4660	15336	2.42	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	63	7		
4130MH0007430021404661C00	4661	15372	2.36	0.0	0.1	15.2	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 4130 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - ~25 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4130MH0008650011404663C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4130MH0002270001304684R00		4684		MOTOR COUNT:		13018		RANGE (cm): 26.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304685S00		4685		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		19-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4130		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4130	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4130MH0008650021404664C00	4664	12922	33.73	-2.8	3.3	125.6	10.8	255	1		
4130MH0008650021404665C00	4665	12946	31.59	-2.5	2.9	118.1	9.5	223	2		
4130MH0008650021304666C00	4666	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	191	3		
4130MH0008650021304667C00	4667	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	159	4		
4130MH0008650021304668C00	4668	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	127	5		
4130MH0008650021304669C00	4669	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	95	6		
4130MH0008650021304670C00	4670	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	63	7		
4130MH0008650021304671C00	4671	13090	22.67	-1.3	1.4	86.7	4.8	31	8		

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SOL 4130 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - ~24 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4130MH0008650011304673C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4130MH0002270001304682R00		4682		MOTOR COUNT:		13033		RANGE (cm): 25.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4130MH0002270001304683S00		4683		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		19-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4130		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL: 4130		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4130MH0008650021304674C00	4674	12937	32.36	-2.6	3.1	120.8	9.9	255	1		
4130MH0008650021304675C00	4675	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	223	2		
4130MH0008650021304676C00	4676	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	191	3		
4130MH0008650021304677C00	4677	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	159	4		
4130MH0008650021304678C00	4678	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	127	5		
4130MH0008650021304679C00	4679	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	95	6		
4130MH0008650021304680C00	4680	13081	23.09	-1.4	1.5	88.2	5.0	63	7		
4130MH0008650021304681C00	4681	13105	22.00	-1.2	1.4	84.3	4.6	31	8		

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SOL 4132 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4132MH0003360011204695C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4132MH0001630000904764R00	4764	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4132MH0001630000904765S00	4765	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4132	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4132	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4132MH0003360021204696C00	4696	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4132MH0003360021204697C00	4697	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4132MH0003360021204698C00	4698	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4132MH0003360021204699C00	4699	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4132MH0003360021204700C00	4700	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4132MH0003360021204701C00	4701	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
4132MH0003360021204702C00	4702	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4132MH0003360021204703C00	4703	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4132 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4132MH0003360011204705C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4132MH0001630001004762R00	4762	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4132MH0001630000904763S00	4763	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4132	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4132	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4132MH0003360021204706C00	4706	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4132MH0003360021204707C00	4707	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4132MH0003360021204708C00	4708	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4132MH0003360021204709C00	4709	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4132MH0003360021204710C00	4710	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4132MH0003360021204711C00	4711	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4132MH0003360021204712C00	4712	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4132MH0003360021204713C00	4713	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4132 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4132MH0008640011204715C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4132MH0001630001004760R00	4760	MOTOR COUNT:		15190	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4132MH0001630001004761S00	4761	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4132	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4132	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4132MH0008640021204716C00	4716	15070	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4132MH0008640021204717C00	4717	15100	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
4132MH0008640021204718C00	4718	15130	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4132MH0008640021204719C00	4719	15160	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
4132MH0008640021204720C00	4720	15190	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
4132MH0008640021204721C00	4721	15220	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6
4132MH0008640021204722C00	4722	15250	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
4132MH0008640021204723C00	4723	15280	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4132 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4132MH0008650011204725C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4132MH0001630001004758R00	4758	MOTOR COUNT:		13024	RANGE (cm):	26.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4132MH0001630001004759S00	4759	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4132	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4132	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4132MH0008650021204726C00	4726	12928	33.17	-2.7	3.2	123.7	10.4	255	1
4132MH0008650021204727C00	4727	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	223	2
4132MH0008650021204728C00	4728	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	191	3
4132MH0008650021204729C00	4729	13000	27.59	-1.9	2.2	104.0	7.2	159	4
4132MH0008650021204730C00	4730	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	127	5
4132MH0008650021204731C00	4731	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	95	6
4132MH0008650021204732C00	4732	13072	23.52	-1.4	1.6	89.7	5.2	63	7
4132MH0008650021204733C00	4733	13096	22.40	-1.3	1.4	85.7	4.7	31	8

UPDATED: 26_March_2024

SOL 4132 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4132MH0008650011204735C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4132MH0001630001004756R00	4756	MOTOR COUNT:		13026	RANGE (cm):	26.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4132MH0001630001004757S00	4757	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4132	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4132		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4132MH0008650021104736C00	4736	12930	32.99	-2.7	3.2	123.0	10.3	255	1
4132MH0008650021104737C00	4737	12954	30.93	-2.4	2.8	115.8	9.1	223	2
4132MH0008650021004738C00	4738	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	191	3
4132MH0008650021004739C00	4739	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
4132MH0008650021004740C00	4740	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	127	5
4132MH0008650021004741C00	4741	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	95	6
4132MH0008650021004742C00	4742	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	63	7
4132MH0008650021004743C00	4743	13098	22.31	-1.3	1.4	85.4	4.7	31	8

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SOL 4132 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4132MH0008650011004745C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4132MH0001630001004754R00	4754	MOTOR COUNT:		13024	RANGE (cm):	26.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4132MH0001630001004755S00	4755	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4132	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4132		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4132MH0008650021004746C00	4746	12928	33.17	-2.7	3.2	123.7	10.4	255	1
4132MH0008650021004747C00	4747	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	223	2
4132MH0008650021004748C00	4748	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	191	3
4132MH0008650021004749C00	4749	13000	27.59	-1.9	2.2	104.0	7.2	159	4
4132MH0008650021004750C00	4750	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	127	5
4132MH0008650021004751C00	4751	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	95	6
4132MH0008650021004752C00	4752	13072	23.52	-1.4	1.6	89.7	5.2	63	7
4132MH0008650021004753C00	4753	13096	22.40	-1.3	1.4	85.7	4.7	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 4000–4133. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 4028, 4030, 4032, 4033, 4035, 4037, 4039, 4040, 4053, 4054, 4056, 4057, 4062, 4067, 4068, 4070, 4071, 4073, 4074, 4076, 4078, 4079, 4082, 4083, 4084, 4088, 4089, 4093, 4098, 4101, 4102, 4105, 4106, 4116, 4117, 4118, 4123, 4127, 4128, 4130, 4132.**

updated: 08_December_2023

Sol 4028 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-Dec-23
camera position	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the Sequoia2 drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_E_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00197	Sequoia2 drill hole drilled on Sol 3980 ~24 cm standoff	4028MH000197001403184C0D	3184	autoFocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Sequoia2 - drilled sol 3980 - standoff near 24 cm
		4028MH000197001403185C0D	3185	drill hole in rock named Sequoia2 - drilled sol 3980 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00774	Sequoia2 drill hole drilled on Sol 3980 ~95 mm standoff	4028MH000774001403186C0D	3186	autoFocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Sequoia2 - drilled sol 3980 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 95 mm
		4028MH000774001403187C0D	3187	drill hole in rock named Sequoia2 - drilled sol 3980 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 95 mm
mN00152	Sequoia2 drill cuttings APXS spot 1 ~ 55 mm standoff	4028MH000152001403188C0D	3188	autoFocus sub-frame for Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4028MH000152001403189C0D	3189	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4028MH000152001403190C0D	3190	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403191C0D	3191	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403192C0D	3192	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403193C0D	3193	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403194C0D	3194	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403195C0D	3195	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403196C0D	3196	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403197C0D	3197	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Sequoia2 drill cuttings APXS spot 2 ~ 55 mm standoff	4028MH000152001403198C0D	3198	autoFocus sub-frame for Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4028MH000152001403199C0D	3199	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4028MH000152001403200C0D	3200	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403201C0D	3201	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403202C0D	3202	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403203C0D	3203	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403204C0D	3204	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403205C0D	3205	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403206C0D	3206	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4028MH000152001403207C0D	3207	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	4028MH000265001403208R0D	3208	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4028 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3200-3207 - best focus image product
		4028MH000265001403209R0D	3209	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4028 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3200-3207 - range map product
		4028MH000265001403210R0D	3210	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4028 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3190-3197 - best focus image product
		4028MH000265001403211R0D	3211	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4028 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3190-3197 - range map product

updated: 11_December_2023

Sol 4030 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		acquired/performed date(s)	0 Dec 23	
		camera positions	6	Image ID:
		total parent images	34	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	40	
MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Keeler_Needle and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Keeler_Needle after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4030MH0019000140321200	3212	autoFocus sub-frame for target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4030MH0019000140321300	3213	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Keeler_Needle after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4030MH0016800140321400	3214	autoFocus sub-frame for target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4030MH0016800140321500	3215	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4030MH0016800140321600	3216	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140321700	3217	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140321800	3218	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140321900	3219	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322000	3220	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322100	3221	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322200	3222	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322300	3223	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Keeler_Needle after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4030MH0016800140322400	3224	autoFocus sub-frame for target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4030MH0016800140322500	3225	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4030MH0016800140322600	3226	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322700	3227	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322800	3228	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140322900	3229	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140323000	3230	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140323100	3231	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140323200	3232	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0016800140323300	3233	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Keeler_Needle after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4030MH0018400140323400	3234	autoFocus sub-frame for target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4030MH0018400140323500	3235	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4030MH0018400140323600	3236	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140323700	3237	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140323800	3238	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140323900	3239	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140324000	3240	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140324100	3241	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140324200	3242	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4030MH0018400140324300	3243	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	4030MH0009500140324400	3244	autoFocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		4030MH0009500140324500	3245	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00189	Focus Merges	4030MH0019300140324600	3246	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3236-3243 - best focus image product
		4030MH0019300140324700	3247	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3236-3243 - range map product
		4030MH0019300140324800	3248	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3226-3233 - best focus image product
		4030MH0019300140324900	3249	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3226-3233 - range map product
		4030MH0019300140325000	3250	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3216-3223 - best focus image product
		4030MH0019300140325100	3251	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3216-3223 - range map product

updated: 14_December_2023

Sol 4032 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities:		MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Wren_Peak. The Robotic Arm faulted after the acquisition of the 15 cm standoff image of Wren_Peak, which precluded the rest of the Sol 4032 MAHLI activities and left MAHLI with the dust cover open above the target.		
acquired/performed date(s)	10-Dec-23	Image ID:		
camera position:	0	total parent images:	2 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	2	focus merges performed:	0	
focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:		
total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	2			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00586	Wren_Peak after DRT ~15 cm standoff	4032MH00586001403252C00	3252	autoFocus sub-frame for target Wren_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 cm
		4032MH005860011403253C00	3253	target Wren_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 cm

updated: 14_December_2023

Sol 4033 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Dec-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

summary of MAHLI activities: A fault occurred onboard the rover on Sol 4032 that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the DRT-brushed target Wren_Peak. Instead, the focus stack images from Sol 4030 imaging of Keeler_Needle and Sol 4028 imaging of APXS spot 2 of Sequoia2 drill cuttings were merged again.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100013	Focus Merges	4033MH0001330001403254R00	3254	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3236-3243 - best focus image product
		4033MH0001330001403255S00	3255	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3236-3243 - range map product
		4033MH0001330001403256R00	3256	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3226-3233 - best focus image product
		4033MH0001330001403257S00	3257	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3226-3233 - range map product
		4033MH0001330001403258R00	3258	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3216-3223 - best focus image product
		4033MH0001330001403259S00	3259	target Keeler_Needle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4030 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3216-3223 - range map product
		4033MH0001330001403260R00	3260	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4028 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3200-3207 - best focus image product
		4033MH0001330001403261S00	3261	Sequoia2 drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4028 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3200-3207 - range map product

updated: 27_August_2024

Sol 4035 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	19-Dec-23	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: The MAHLI dust cover was closed after the Sol 4032 Robotic Arm fault. MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Wren_Peak (brushed on Sol 4032) and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Wren_Peak after Sol 4032 DRT ~25 cm standoff	4035MH00190001403262C0D	3262	autofocus sub-frame for target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4035MH00190001403263C0D	3263	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00198	Wren_Peak after Sol 4032 DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4035MH00168001403264C0D	3264	autofocus sub-frame for target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4035MH00168001403265C0D	3265	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4035MH00168001403266C0D	3266	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403267C0D	3267	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403268C0D	3268	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403269C0D	3269	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403270C0D	3270	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403271C0D	3271	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403272C0D	3272	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403273C0D	3273	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00198	Wren_Peak after Sol 4032 DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4035MH00168001403274C0D	3274	autofocus sub-frame for target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4035MH00168001403275C0D	3275	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4035MH00168001403276C0D	3276	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403277C0D	3277	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403278C0D	3278	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403279C0D	3279	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403280C0D	3280	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403281C0D	3281	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403282C0D	3282	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00168001403283C0D	3283	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Wren_Peak after Sol 4032 DRT ~2 cm standoff	4035MH00302001403284C0D	3284	autofocus sub-frame for target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4035MH00302001403285C0D	3285	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4035MH00302001403286C0D	3286	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403287C0D	3287	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403288C0D	3288	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403289C0D	3289	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403290C0D	3290	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403291C0D	3291	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403292C0D	3292	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4035MH00302001403293C0D	3293	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4035MH00193001403294C0D	3294	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4035 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3286-3293 - best focus image product
		4035MH00193001403295C0D	3295	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4035 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3286-3293 - range map product
		4035MH00193001403296C0D	3296	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4035 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3276-3283 - best focus image product
		4035MH00193001403297C0D	3297	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4035 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3276-3283 - range map product
		4035MH00193001403298C0D	3298	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4035 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3266-3273 - best focus image product
		4035MH00193001403299C0D	3299	target Wren_Peak - after sol 4032 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4035 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3266-3273 - range map product

updated: 15_December_2023

Sol 4037 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-Dec-23
camera position	0
total parent images	6
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Potluck_Pass.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Potluck_Pass *24 cm standoff	4037MH00190001403300C00	3300	autoFocus sub-frame for target Potluck_Pass - standoff near 24 cm
		4037MH00190011403301C00	3301	target Potluck_Pass - standoff near 24 cm
mN00148	Potluck_Pass stereo-1 *9 cm standoff	4037MH00148001403302C00	3302	autoFocus sub-frame for target Potluck_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		4037MH00148011403303C00	3303	target Potluck_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
mN00148	Potluck_Pass stereo-2 *9 cm standoff	4037MH00148001403304C00	3304	autoFocus sub-frame for target Potluck_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		4037MH00148011403305C00	3305	target Potluck_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm

updated: 30_December_2023

Sol 4039 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Dec-23
camera position	40
total parent images	95
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	95

Image ID: black = best, best-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Arrow_Peak and the target Four_Gables.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Arrow_Peak after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4039MH00190001403306C00	3306	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4039MH00190001403307C00	3307	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Arrow_Peak after DRT stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00168001403308C00	3308	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00168001403309C00	3309	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00168001403310C00	3310	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403311C00	3311	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403312C00	3312	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403313C00	3313	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403314C00	3314	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403315C00	3315	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403316C00	3316	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403317C00	3317	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Arrow_Peak after DRT stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00168001403318C00	3318	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00168001403319C00	3319	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00168001403320C00	3320	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403321C00	3321	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403322C00	3322	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403323C00	3323	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403324C00	3324	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403325C00	3325	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403326C00	3326	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00168001403327C00	3327	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Arrow_Peak after DRT relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00705001403328C00	3328	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00705001403329C00	3329	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Arrow_Peak after DRT relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00705001403330C00	3330	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00705001403331C00	3331	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Arrow_Peak after DRT relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00705001403332C00	3332	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00705001403333C00	3333	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00743	Arrow_Peak after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4039MH00743001403334C00	3334	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4039MH00743001403335C00	3335	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4039MH00743001403336C00	3336	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403337C00	3337	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403338C00	3338	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403339C00	3339	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403340C00	3340	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403341C00	3341	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403342C00	3342	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00743001403343C00	3343	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Four_Gables ~25 cm standoff	4039MH00190001403344C00	3344	autofocus sub-frame for target Four_Gables - standoff near 25 cm
		4039MH00190001403345C00	3345	target Four_Gables - standoff near 25 cm
mN00297	Four_Gables stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00297001403346C00	3346	autofocus sub-frame for target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00297001403347C00	3347	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00297001403348C00	3348	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403349C00	3349	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403350C00	3350	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403351C00	3351	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403352C00	3352	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403353C00	3353	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403354C00	3354	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403355C00	3355	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Four_Gables stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4039MH00297001403356C00	3356	autofocus sub-frame for target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00297001403357C00	3357	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4039MH00297001403358C00	3358	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403359C00	3359	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403360C00	3360	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403361C00	3361	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403362C00	3362	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403363C00	3363	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403364C00	3364	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4039MH00297001403365C00	3365	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 19_December_2023

Sol 4040 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Dec-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4039 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4040MH0002270001403366R00	3366	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3358-3365 - best focus image product
		4040MH0002270001403367S00	3367	target Four_Gables - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3358-3365 - range map product
		4040MH0002270001403368R00	3368	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3348-3355 - best focus image product
		4040MH0002270001403369S00	3369	target Four_Gables - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3348-3355 - range map product
		4040MH0002270001403370R00	3370	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3336-3343 - best focus image product
		4040MH0002270001403371S00	3371	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3336-3343 - range map product
		4040MH0002270001403372R00	3372	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3320-3327 - best focus image product
		4040MH0002270001403373S00	3373	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3320-3327 - range map product
		4040MH0002270001403374R00	3374	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3310-3317 - best focus image product
		4040MH0002270001403375S00	3375	target Arrow_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4039 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3310-3317 - range map product

updated: 04_January_2024

Sol 4053 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Dec-23
camera position	92
total parent images	92 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	92
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Moose_Lake and the target Lewis_Creek. MAHLI also imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Moose_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	405MH00190001403376CD	3376	autofocus sub-frame for target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		405MH00190001403377CD	3377	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Moose_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00168001403378CD	3378	autofocus sub-frame for target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00168001403379CD	3379	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00168001403380CD	3380	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403381CD	3381	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403382CD	3382	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403383CD	3383	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403384CD	3384	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403385CD	3385	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403386CD	3386	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403387CD	3387	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Moose_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00168001403388CD	3388	autofocus sub-frame for target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00168001403389CD	3389	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00168001403390CD	3390	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403391CD	3391	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403392CD	3392	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403393CD	3393	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403394CD	3394	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403395CD	3395	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403396CD	3396	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00168001403397CD	3397	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Moose_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	405MH00743001403398CD	3398	autofocus sub-frame for target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		405MH00743001403399CD	3399	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		405MH00743001403400CD	3400	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403401CD	3401	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403402CD	3402	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403403CD	3403	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403404CD	3404	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403405CD	3405	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403406CD	3406	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00743001403407CD	3407	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Lewis_Creek ~25 cm standoff	405MH00190001403408CD	3408	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 25 cm
		405MH00190001403409CD	3409	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Lewis_Creek stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00182001403410CD	3410	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00182001403411CD	3411	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00182001403412CD	3412	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403413CD	3413	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403414CD	3414	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403415CD	3415	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403416CD	3416	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403417CD	3417	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403418CD	3418	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403419CD	3419	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Lewis_Creek stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00182001403420CD	3420	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00182001403421CD	3421	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00182001403422CD	3422	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403423CD	3423	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403424CD	3424	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403425CD	3425	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403426CD	3426	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403427CD	3427	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403428CD	3428	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405MH00182001403429CD	3429	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Lewis_Creek relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00705001403430CD	3430	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00705001403431CD	3431	target Lewis_Creek - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Lewis_Creek relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00705001403432CD	3432	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00705001403433CD	3433	target Lewis_Creek - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Lewis_Creek relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	405MH00705001403434CD	3434	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		405MH00705001403435CD	3435	target Lewis_Creek - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm

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mNH00426	Lewis_Creek +1 cm standoff	405BMH000426001403436C00	3436	autofocus sub-frame for target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm
		405BMH000426001403437C00	3437	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm
		405BMH000426001403438C00	3438	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405BMH000426001403439C00	3439	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405BMH000426001403440C00	3440	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405BMH000426001403441C00	3441	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405BMH000426001403442C00	3442	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405BMH000426001403443C00	3443	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		405BMH000426001403444C00	3444	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
405BMH000426001403445C00	3445	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNH00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHJ looking at the sky opposite the sun at +100° azimuth, +40° elevation, away from the rover deck	405BMH000712001403446C00	3446	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
		405BMH000712001403447C00	3447	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		405BMH000712001403448C00	3448	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm
		405BMH000712001403449C00	3449	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm
		405BMH000712001403450C00	3450	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus
mNH00463	sky flats - MAHJ looking at the sky opposite the sun at +100° azimuth, +40° elevation, away from the rover deck	405BMH000430001403451C00	3451	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
		405BMH000430001403452C00	3452	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		405BMH000430001403453C00	3453	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm
		405BMH000430001403454C00	3454	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm
		405BMH000430001403455C00	3455	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm
mNH00463	sky flats - MAHJ looking at the sky opposite the sun at +100° azimuth, +40° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	405BMH000430001403457C00	3457	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000430001403458C00	3458	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000430001403459C00	3459	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000430001403460C00	3460	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000430001403461C00	3461	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
mNH00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHJ looking at the sky opposite the sun at +100° azimuth, +40° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	405BMH000712001403463C00	3463	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000712001403464C00	3464	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000712001403465C00	3465	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000712001403466C00	3466	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		405BMH000712001403467C00	3467	MAHJ sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol

updated: 02_January_2024

Sol 4054 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	1-Jan-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4053 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	4054MH001630001403468R00	3468	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3438-3445 - best focus image product
		4054MH001630001403469S00	3469	target Lewis_Creek - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3438-3445 - range map product
		4054MH001630001403470R00	3470	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3422-3429 - best focus image product
		4054MH001630001403471S00	3471	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3422-3429 - range map product
		4054MH001630001403472R00	3472	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3412-3419 - best focus image product
		4054MH001630001403473S00	3473	target Lewis_Creek - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3412-3419 - range map product
		4054MH001630001403474R00	3474	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3400-3407 - best focus image product
		4054MH001630001403475S00	3475	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3400-3407 - range map product
		4054MH001630001403476R00	3476	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3390-3397 - best focus image product
		4054MH001630001403477S00	3477	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3390-3397 - range map product
		4054MH001630001403478R00	3478	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3380-3387 - best focus image product
		4054MH001630001403479S00	3479	target Moose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4053 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3380-3387 - range map product

updated: 08_January_2024

Sol 4056 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	3 Jan 24	
		camera position	65	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	65	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed targets Green_Pass and Wanda_Lake. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the ChemMin inlet for cleanliness.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Green_Pass after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4056MH00190001403480C00	3480	autofocus sub-frame for target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4056MH00190001403481C00	3481	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Green_Pass after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4056MH00168001403482C00	3482	autofocus sub-frame for target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403483C00	3483	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403484C00	3484	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403485C00	3485	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403486C00	3486	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403487C00	3487	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403488C00	3488	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403489C00	3489	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403490C00	3490	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403491C00	3491	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Green_Pass after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4056MH00168001403492C00	3492	autofocus sub-frame for target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403493C00	3493	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403494C00	3494	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403495C00	3495	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403496C00	3496	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403497C00	3497	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403498C00	3498	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403499C00	3499	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403500C00	3500	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403501C00	3501	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Green_Pass after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4056MH00743001403502C00	3502	autofocus sub-frame for target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4056MH00743001403503C00	3503	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4056MH00743001403504C00	3504	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403505C00	3505	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403506C00	3506	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403507C00	3507	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403508C00	3508	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403509C00	3509	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403510C00	3510	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00743001403511C00	3511	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Wanda_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4056MH00190001403512C00	3512	autofocus sub-frame for target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4056MH00190001403513C00	3513	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Wanda_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4056MH00168001403514C00	3514	autofocus sub-frame for target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403515C00	3515	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403516C00	3516	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403517C00	3517	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403518C00	3518	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403519C00	3519	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403520C00	3520	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403521C00	3521	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403522C00	3522	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403523C00	3523	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Wanda_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4056MH00168001403524C00	3524	autofocus sub-frame for target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403525C00	3525	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4056MH00168001403526C00	3526	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403527C00	3527	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403528C00	3528	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403529C00	3529	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403530C00	3530	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403531C00	3531	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403532C00	3532	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00168001403533C00	3533	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Wanda_Lake after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4056MH00302001403534C00	3534	autofocus sub-frame for target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4056MH00302001403535C00	3535	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4056MH00302001403536C00	3536	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403537C00	3537	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403538C00	3538	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403539C00	3539	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403540C00	3540	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403541C00	3541	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403542C00	3542	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4056MH00302001403543C00	3543	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above ChemMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; otherwise same as above	4056MH00312001403544C00	3544	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		4056MH00312001403545C00	3545	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN00326	position 2 of 3; otherwise same as above	4056MH00326001403546C00	3546	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	position 3 of 3; otherwise same as two above	4056MH00326001403547C00	3547	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	~19 cm above open ChemMin inlet	4056MH00326001403548C00	3548	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 05_January_2024

Sol 4057 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6-Jan-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	13
total parent images + focus merge products:	13

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4056 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4057MH001630001403549000	3549	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3536-3543 - best focus image product
		4057MH001630001403550500	3550	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3536-3543 - range map product
		4057MH001630001403551000	3551	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3526-3533 - best focus image product
		4057MH001630001403552500	3552	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3526-3533 - range map product
		4057MH001630001403553000	3553	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3516-3523 - best focus image product
		4057MH001630001403554500	3554	target Wanda_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3516-3523 - range map product
		4057MH001630001403555000	3555	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3504-3511 - best focus image product
		4057MH001630001403556500	3556	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3504-3511 - range map product
		4057MH001630001403557000	3557	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3494-3501 - best focus image product
		4057MH001630001403558500	3558	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3494-3501 - range map product
		4057MH001630001403559000	3559	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3484-3491 - best focus image product
		4057MH001630001403560500	3560	target Green_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4056 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3484-3491 - range map product

updated: 11_January_2024

Sol 4062 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	9-Jan-24	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Chagooopa and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Chagooopa after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4062MH001900001403561C00	3561	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4062MH001900011403562C00	3562	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Chagooopa after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4062MH001680001403563C00	3563	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4062MH001680011403564C00	3564	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4062MH001680021403565C00	3565	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680031403566C00	3566	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680041403567C00	3567	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680051403568C00	3568	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680061403569C00	3569	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680071403570C00	3570	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680081403571C00	3571	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680091403572C00	3572	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Chagooopa after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4062MH001680001403573C00	3573	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4062MH001680011403574C00	3574	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4062MH001680021403575C00	3575	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680031403576C00	3576	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680041403577C00	3577	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680051403578C00	3578	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680061403579C00	3579	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680071403580C00	3580	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680081403581C00	3581	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH001680091403582C00	3582	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Chagooopa after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4062MH003020011403583C00	3583	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4062MH003020021403584C00	3584	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4062MH003020031403585C00	3585	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020041403586C00	3586	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020051403587C00	3587	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020061403588C00	3588	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020071403589C00	3589	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020081403590C00	3590	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020091403591C00	3591	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4062MH003020011403592C00	3592	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4062MH001930001403593R00	3593	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4062 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3585-3592 - best focus image product
		4062MH001930001403594R00	3594	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4062 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3585-3592 - range map product
		4062MH001930001403595R00	3595	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4062 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3575-3582 - best focus image product
		4062MH001930001403596R00	3596	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4062 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3575-3582 - range map product
		4062MH001930001403597R00	3597	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4062 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3565-3572 - best focus image product
		4062MH001930001403598R00	3598	target Chagooopa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4062 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3565-3572 - range map product

updated: 18_January_2024

Sol 4067 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15_Jan_24
camera position	6
total parent images	44
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	44

MAHLI imaged the targets Split_Mountain and Great_Western_Divide.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Split_Mountain ~25 cm standoff	4067MH0001900001403599ZC0D	3599	autofocus sub-frame for target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4067MH0001900011403600ZC0D	3600	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN002224	Split_Mountain APXS spot 1 ~55 mm standoff	4067MH000224001403601ZC0D	3601	autofocus sub-frame for target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403602ZC0D	3602	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403603ZC0D	3603	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403604ZC0D	3604	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403605ZC0D	3605	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403606ZC0D	3606	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403607ZC0D	3607	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403608ZC0D	3608	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403609ZC0D	3609	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403610ZC0D	3610	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002224	Split_Mountain APXS spot 2 ~55 mm standoff	4067MH000224001403611ZC0D	3611	autofocus sub-frame for target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403612ZC0D	3612	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403613ZC0D	3613	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403614ZC0D	3614	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403615ZC0D	3615	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403616ZC0D	3616	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403617ZC0D	3617	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403618ZC0D	3618	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403619ZC0D	3619	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403620ZC0D	3620	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002224	Split_Mountain APXS spot 3 ~55 mm standoff	4067MH000224001403621ZC0D	3621	autofocus sub-frame for target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403622ZC0D	3622	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403623ZC0D	3623	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403624ZC0D	3624	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403625ZC0D	3625	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403626ZC0D	3626	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403627ZC0D	3627	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403628ZC0D	3628	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403629ZC0D	3629	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403630ZC0D	3630	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002224	Split_Mountain APXS spot 4 ~55 mm standoff	4067MH000224001403631ZC0D	3631	autofocus sub-frame for target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403632ZC0D	3632	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm
		4067MH000224001403633ZC0D	3633	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403634ZC0D	3634	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403635ZC0D	3635	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403636ZC0D	3636	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403637ZC0D	3637	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403638ZC0D	3638	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403639ZC0D	3639	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4067MH000224001403640ZC0D	3640	target Split_Mountain - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002190	Great_Western_Divide ~27 cm standoff	4067MH0001900001403641ZC0D	3641	autofocus sub-frame for target Great_Western_Divide - standoff near 27 cm
		4067MH0001900011403642ZC0D	3642	target Great_Western_Divide - standoff near 27 cm

updated: 16_January_2024

Sol 4068 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	ES-200-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4067 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	4068MH001530001403643R00	3643	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3633-3640 - best focus image product
		4068MH001530001403644S00	3644	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 4 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3633-3640 - range map product
		4068MH001530001403645R00	3645	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3620-3630 - best focus image product
		4068MH001530001403646S00	3646	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3620-3630 - range map product
		4068MH001530001403647R00	3647	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3610-3620 - best focus image product
		4068MH001530001403648S00	3648	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3610-3620 - range map product
		4068MH001530001403649R00	3649	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3600-3610 - best focus image product
		4068MH001530001403650S00	3650	target Split_Mountain - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4067 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3600-3610 - range map product

updated: 19_January_2024

Sol 4071 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19_Jan_24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4070 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	4071MH000163000140371900	3715	target Dorst - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3707-3714 - best focus image product
		4071MH0001630001403716500	3716	target Dorst - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3707-3714 - range map product
		4071MH000163000140371700	3717	target Dorst - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3697-3704 - best focus image product
		4071MH0001630001403718500	3718	target Dorst - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3697-3704 - range map product
		4071MH000163000140371900	3719	target Dorst - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3687-3694 - best focus image product
		4071MH0001630001403720500	3720	target Dorst - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3687-3694 - range map product
		4071MH000163000140372100	3721	target Scheelite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3675-3682 - best focus image product
		4071MH0001630001403722500	3722	target Scheelite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3675-3682 - range map product
		4071MH000163000140372300	3723	target Scheelite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3665-3672 - best focus image product
		4071MH0001630001403724500	3724	target Scheelite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3665-3672 - range map product
		4071MH000163000140372500	3725	target Scheelite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3655-3662 - best focus image product
		4071MH0001630001403726500	3726	target Scheelite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4070 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3655-3662 - range map product

updated: 23_January_2024

Sol 4074 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Jan-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4073 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4074MH00163000140379300	3793	target Sleeping_Beauty_Tower - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3785-3792 - best focus image product
		4074MH00163000140379400	3794	target Sleeping_Beauty_Tower - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3785-3792 - range map product
		4074MH00163000140379500	3795	target Sleeping_Beauty_Tower - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3770-3782 - best focus image product
		4074MH00163000140379600	3796	target Sleeping_Beauty_Tower - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3775-3782 - range map product
		4074MH00163000140379700	3797	target Sleeping_Beauty_Tower - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3743-3772 - best focus image product
		4074MH00163000140379800	3798	target Sleeping_Beauty_Tower - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3745-3772 - range map product
		4074MH00163000140379900	3799	target Mount_Langley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3751-3758 - best focus image product
		4074MH00163000140380000	3800	target Mount_Langley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3751-3758 - range map product
		4074MH00163000140380100	3801	target Mount_Langley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3741-3748 - best focus image product
		4074MH00163000140380200	3802	target Mount_Langley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3741-3748 - range map product
		4074MH00163000140380300	3803	target Mount_Langley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3731-3738 - best focus image product
		4074MH00163000140380400	3804	target Mount_Langley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4073 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3731-3738 - range map product

updated: 25_January_2024

Sol 4076 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26 Jan 24
camera position	6
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Manzanita and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Manzanita after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4076MH0019000140380500	3805	autoFocus sub-frame for target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4076MH0019000140380600	3806	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Manzanita after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4076MH0016800140380700	3807	autoFocus sub-frame for target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4076MH0016800140380800	3808	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4076MH0016800140380900	3809	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381000	3810	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381100	3811	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381200	3812	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381300	3813	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381400	3814	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381500	3815	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140381600	3816	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Manzanita after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4076MH0016800140381700	3817	autoFocus sub-frame for target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4076MH0016800140381800	3818	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4076MH0016800140381900	3819	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382000	3820	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382100	3821	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382200	3822	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382300	3823	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382400	3824	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382500	3825	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0016800140382600	3826	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Manzanita after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4076MH0030200140382700	3827	autoFocus sub-frame for target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4076MH0030200140382800	3828	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4076MH0030200140382900	3829	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383000	3830	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383100	3831	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383200	3832	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383300	3833	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383400	3834	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383500	3835	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4076MH0030200140383600	3836	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4076MH0019300140383700	3837	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4076 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3829-3836 - best focus image product
		4076MH0019300140383800	3838	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4076 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3829-3836 - range map product
		4076MH0019300140383900	3839	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4076 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3819-3826 - best focus image product
		4076MH0019300140384000	3840	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4076 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3819-3826 - range map product
		4076MH0019300140384100	3841	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4076 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3809-3816 - best focus image product
		4076MH0019300140384200	3842	target Manzanita - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4076 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3809-3816 - range map product

updated: 29_January_2024

Sol 4078 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	26-Jan-24	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Sierra_Columbine and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sierra_Columbine after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4078MH00190001403843C0D	3843	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4078MH00190001403844C0D	3844	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Sierra_Columbine after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4078MH00182001403845C0D	3845	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4078MH00182001403846C0D	3846	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4078MH00182001403847C0D	3847	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403848C0D	3848	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403849C0D	3849	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403850C0D	3850	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403851C0D	3851	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403852C0D	3852	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403853C0D	3853	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403854C0D	3854	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Sierra_Columbine after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4078MH00182001403855C0D	3855	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4078MH00182001403856C0D	3856	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4078MH00182001403857C0D	3857	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403858C0D	3858	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403859C0D	3859	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403860C0D	3860	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403861C0D	3861	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403862C0D	3862	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403863C0D	3863	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00182001403864C0D	3864	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00796	Sierra_Columbine after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4078MH00796001403865C0D	3865	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4078MH00796001403866C0D	3866	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4078MH00796001403867C0D	3867	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403868C0D	3868	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403869C0D	3869	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403870C0D	3870	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403871C0D	3871	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403872C0D	3872	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403873C0D	3873	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4078MH00796001403874C0D	3874	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	4078MH00193001403875C0D	3875	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3867-3874 - best focus image product
		4078MH00193001403876C0D	3876	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3867-3874 - range map product
		4078MH00193001403877C0D	3877	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3857-3864 - best focus image product
		4078MH00193001403878C0D	3878	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3857-3864 - range map product
		4078MH00193001403879C0D	3879	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3847-3854 - best focus image product
		4078MH00193001403880C0D	3880	target Sierra_Columbine - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3847-3854 - range map product

mnh00163	Focus Merge	4078MH00163000140394500	3945	target Lake_Sabrina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3937-3944 - best focus image product
		4078MH001630001403946500	3946	target Lake_Sabrina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3937-3944 - range map product
		4078MH001630001403947000	3947	target Lake_Sabrina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3927-3934 - best focus image product
		4078MH001630001403948500	3948	target Lake_Sabrina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3927-3934 - range map product
		4078MH001630001403949000	3949	target Lake_Sabrina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3917-3924 - best focus image product
		4078MH001630001403950500	3950	target Lake_Sabrina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3917-3924 - range map product
		4078MH001630001403951000	3951	target Simpson_Meadow - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3905-3912 - best focus image product
		4078MH001630001403952500	3952	target Simpson_Meadow - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3905-3912 - range map product
		4078MH001630001403953000	3953	target Simpson_Meadow - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3895-3902 - best focus image product
		4078MH001630001403954500	3954	target Simpson_Meadow - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3895-3902 - range map product
		4078MH001630001403955000	3955	target Simpson_Meadow - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3885-3892 - best focus image product
		4078MH001630001403956500	3956	target Simpson_Meadow - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4079 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3885-3892 - range map product

Sol 4082 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30 Jan 24
camera position	12
total parent images	95
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	95

Image ID: black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target June_Lake, the target Deerhorn_Mountain and the DRT-brushed target Marth_Lake.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	June_Lake before DRT ~25 cm standoff	4082MH001900001403957C00	3957	autofocus sub-frame for target June_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4082MH001900011403958C00	3958	target June_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	June_Lake before DRT ~5 cm standoff	4082MH001220011403959C00	3959	autofocus sub-frame for target June_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		4082MH001220011403960C00	3960	target June_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	June_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4082MH001900001403961C00	3961	autofocus sub-frame for target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4082MH001900011403962C00	3962	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	June_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4082MH001680011403963C00	3963	autofocus sub-frame for target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4082MH001680011403964C00	3964	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4082MH001680021403965C00	3965	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403966C00	3966	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403967C00	3967	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403968C00	3968	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403969C00	3969	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403970C00	3970	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403971C00	3971	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680021403972C00	3972	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	June_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4082MH001680031403973C00	3973	autofocus sub-frame for target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4082MH001680031403974C00	3974	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4082MH001680031403975C00	3975	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403976C00	3976	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403977C00	3977	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403978C00	3978	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403979C00	3979	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403980C00	3980	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403981C00	3981	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH001680031403982C00	3982	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	June_Lake after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4082MH003020011403983C00	3983	autofocus sub-frame for target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4082MH003020011403984C00	3984	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4082MH003020021403985C00	3985	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403986C00	3986	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403987C00	3987	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403988C00	3988	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403989C00	3989	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403990C00	3990	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403991C00	3991	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH003020021403992C00	3992	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Deerhorn_Mountain ~24 cm standoff	4082MH001900001403993C00	3993	autofocus sub-frame for target Deerhorn_Mountain - standoff near 24 cm
		4082MH001900011403994C00	3994	target Deerhorn_Mountain - standoff near 24 cm
mN00841	Deerhorn_Mountain stereo-1 ~14 cm standoff	4082MH008410011403995C00	3995	autofocus sub-frame for target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm
		4082MH008410011403996C00	3996	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm
		4082MH008410021403997C00	3997	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021403998C00	3998	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021403999C00	3999	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021404000C00	4000	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021404001C00	4001	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021404002C00	4002	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021404003C00	4003	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410021404004C00	4004	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00841	Deerhorn_Mountain stereo-2 ~14 cm standoff	4082MH008410031404005C00	4005	autofocus sub-frame for target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		4082MH008410031404006C00	4006	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		4082MH008410031404007C00	4007	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404008C00	4008	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404009C00	4009	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404010C00	4010	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404011C00	4011	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404012C00	4012	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404013C00	4013	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4082MH008410031404014C00	4014	target Deerhorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Martha_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4082MH001900001404015C00	4015	autofocus sub-frame for target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4082MH001900011404016C00	4016	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm

Continued on Next Page...

updated: 25_April_2024

Sol 4083 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25_Apr_24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4082 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00170	Focus Merges	40E3MH0001700001404047900	4047	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4039-4046 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404048500	4048	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4039-4046 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404049900	4049	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4023-4036 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404050500	4050	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4023-4036 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404051900	4051	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4013-4026 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404052500	4052	target Martha_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4013-4026 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404053900	4053	target Deershorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4007-4014 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404054500	4054	target Deershorn_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4007-4014 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404055900	4055	target Deershorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3997-4004 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404056500	4056	target Deershorn_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3997-4004 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404057900	4057	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3981-3992 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404058500	4058	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3981-3992 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404059900	4059	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3975-3982 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404060500	4060	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3975-3982 - range map product
		40E3MH0001700001404061900	4061	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3965-3972 - best focus image product
		40E3MH0001700001404062500	4062	target June_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4082 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3965-3972 - range map product

updated: 28_February_2024

Sol 4084 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	0-Feb-24	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Grizzly_Lakes and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Grizzly_Lakes after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4084MH0001900001404063C00	4063	autofocus sub-frame for target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4084MH0001900011404064C00	4064	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Grizzly_Lakes after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4084MH0001680001404065C00	4065	autofocus sub-frame for target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4084MH0001680011404066C00	4066	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4084MH0001680021404067C00	4067	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680031404068C00	4068	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680041404069C00	4069	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680051404070C00	4070	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680061404071C00	4071	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680071404072C00	4072	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680081404073C00	4073	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680091404074C00	4074	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Grizzly_Lakes after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4084MH0001680001404075C00	4075	autofocus sub-frame for target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4084MH0001680011404076C00	4076	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4084MH0001680021404077C00	4077	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680031404078C00	4078	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680041404079C00	4079	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680051404080C00	4080	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680061404081C00	4081	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680071404082C00	4082	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680081404083C00	4083	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0001680091404084C00	4084	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Grizzly_Lakes after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4084MH0007430001404085C00	4085	autofocus sub-frame for target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4084MH0007430011404086C00	4086	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4084MH0007430021404087C00	4087	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430031404088C00	4088	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430041404089C00	4089	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430051404090C00	4090	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430061404091C00	4091	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430071404092C00	4092	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430081404093C00	4093	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4084MH0007430091404094C00	4094	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4084MH0001930001404095R00	4095	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4084 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4087-4094 - best focus image product
		4084MH0001930011404096S00	4096	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4084 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4087-4094 - range map product
		4084MH0001930021404097R00	4097	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4084 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4077-4084 - best focus image product
		4084MH0001930031404098S00	4098	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4084 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4077-4084 - range map product
		4084MH0001930041404099R00	4099	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4084 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4067-4074 - best focus image product
		4084MH0001930051404100S00	4100	target Grizzly_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4084 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4067-4074 - range map product

updated: 05_February_2024

Sol 4088 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0-Feb-24
camera position	20
total parent images	20
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	20

MAHLI imaged 2367 of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4088MH0076900140410101	4101	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4088MH0077000140410201	4102	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4088MH0077100140410301	4103	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4088MH0077200140410401	4104	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4088MH0076900140410501	4105	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4088MH0077000140410601	4106	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4088MH0077100140410701	4107	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4088MH0077200140410801	4108	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4088MH0076900140410901	4109	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4088MH0077000140411001	4110	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4088MH0077100140411101	4111	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4088MH0077200140411201	4112	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4088MH0076900140411301	4113	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4088MH0077000140411401	4114	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4088MH0077100140411501	4115	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4088MH0077200140411601	4116	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4088MH0076900140411701	4117	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4088MH0077000140411801	4118	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4088MH0077100140411901	4119	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4088MH0077200140412001	4120	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4088 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm

updated: 28_February_2024

Sol 4089 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6-Feb-24
camera position	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Willow_Springs, which included a checkout of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Willow_Springs ~25 cm standoff	4089MH00190001404121C00	4121	autoFocus sub-frame for target Willow_Springs - standoff near 25 cm
		4089MH00190001404122C00	4122	target Willow_Springs - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Willow_Springs stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4089MH00182001404123C00	4123	autoFocus sub-frame for target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4089MH00182001404124C00	4124	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4089MH00182001404125C00	4125	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404126C00	4126	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404127C00	4127	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404128C00	4128	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404129C00	4129	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404130C00	4130	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404131C00	4131	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404132C00	4132	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Willow_Springs stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4089MH00182001404133C00	4133	autoFocus sub-frame for target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4089MH00182001404134C00	4134	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4089MH00182001404135C00	4135	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404136C00	4136	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404137C00	4137	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404138C00	4138	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404139C00	4139	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404140C00	4140	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404141C00	4141	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4089MH00182001404142C00	4142	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00866	Willow_Springs MAHLI prox mode checkout ~5 cm standoff	4089MH000866001404143C00	4143	autoFocus sub-frame for target Willow_Springs - MAHLI proximity mode checkout - standoff near 5 cm
		4089MH000866001404144C00	4144	target Willow_Springs - MAHLI proximity mode checkout - standoff near 5 cm
mN00265	Focus Merges	4089MH00265001404145R00	4145	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4089 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4135-4142 - best focus image product
		4089MH00265001404146S00	4146	target Willow_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4089 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4135-4142 - range map product
		4089MH00265001404147R00	4147	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4089 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4123-4132 - best focus image product
		4089MH00265001404148S00	4148	target Willow_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4089 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4123-4132 - range map product

Sol 4093 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	10-Feb-24	
		camera position	75	Image ID:
		total parent images	5	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images - focus merge products	10	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the target Iridescent_Lake and DRT brushed target The_Miter. A test to see how the performance of the DRT compares at different distances above the surface of a target was done on the target The_Miter. The DRT was used to brush the target The_Miter at the height of 19 mm standoff, 17 mm standoff and the standard height of 15 mm standoff. MAHLI was used to document the surface before it was brushed and after the three brush events. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Iridescent_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4093MH00190001404149X00	4149	autofocus sub-frame for target Iridescent_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4093MH00190001404150X00	4150	target Iridescent_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Iridescent_Lake stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4093MH00182001404151X00	4151	autofocus sub-frame for target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4093MH00182001404152X00	4152	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4093MH00182001404153X00	4153	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404154X00	4154	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404155X00	4155	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404156X00	4156	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404157X00	4157	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404158X00	4158	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404159X00	4159	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404160X00	4160	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Iridescent_Lake stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4093MH00182001404161X00	4161	autofocus sub-frame for target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4093MH00182001404162X00	4162	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4093MH00182001404163X00	4163	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404164X00	4164	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404165X00	4165	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404166X00	4166	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404167X00	4167	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404168X00	4168	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404169X00	4169	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00182001404170X00	4170	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00586	The_Miter before DRT ~15 cm standoff	4093MH00586001404171X00	4171	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 cm
		4093MH00586001404172X00	4172	target The_Miter - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 cm
mN00212	The_Miter before DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00122001404173X00	4173	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00122001404174X00	4174	target The_Miter - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00212	The_Miter before DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00122001404175X00	4175	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00122001404176X00	4176	target The_Miter - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00586	The_Miter after DRT from height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 ~15 cm standoff	4093MH00586001404177X00	4177	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
		4093MH00586001404178X00	4178	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
mN00212	The_Miter after DRT from height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00122001404179X00	4179	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00122001404180X00	4180	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00212	The_Miter after DRT from height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00122001404181X00	4181	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00122001404182X00	4182	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00586	The_Miter after DRT from height of 17 mm standoff ~15 cm standoff	4093MH00586001404183X00	4183	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
		4093MH00586001404184X00	4184	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
mN00212	The_Miter after DRT from height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-1 ~15 mm standoff	4093MH00122001404185X00	4185	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 mm
		4093MH00122001404186X00	4186	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 mm
mN00212	The_Miter after DRT from height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00122001404187X00	4187	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00122001404188X00	4188	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00586	The_Miter after DRT ~15 cm standoff	4093MH00586001404189X00	4189	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
		4093MH00586001404190X00	4190	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
mN00168	The_Miter after DRT from height of 15 mm standoff stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00168001404191X00	4191	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00168001404192X00	4192	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00168001404193X00	4193	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404194X00	4194	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404195X00	4195	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404196X00	4196	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404197X00	4197	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404198X00	4198	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404199X00	4199	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404200X00	4200	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	The_Miter after DRT from height of 15 mm standoff stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4093MH00168001404201X00	4201	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00168001404202X00	4202	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4093MH00168001404203X00	4203	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404204X00	4204	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404205X00	4205	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404206X00	4206	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404207X00	4207	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404208X00	4208	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404209X00	4209	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH00168001404210X00	4210	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mH00302	The_Miter after DRT from height of 15 mm standoff ~2 cm standoff	4093MH00302001404214C00	4211	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm
		4093MH003020011404212C00	4212	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm
		4093MH003020021404213C00	4213	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404214C00	4214	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404215C00	4215	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404216C00	4216	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404217C00	4217	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404218C00	4218	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404219C00	4219	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4093MH003020021404220C00	4220	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00227	Focus Merges	4093MH002270001404218R00	4221	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - Focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4213-4220 - best focus image product
		4093MH002270001404225R00	4222	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 2 cm - Focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4213-4220 - range map product
		4093MH002270001404238R00	4223	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4203-4210 - best focus image product
		4093MH002270001404245R00	4224	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4203-4210 - range map product
		4093MH002270001404255R00	4225	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4193-4200 - best focus image product
		4093MH002270001404265R00	4226	target The_Miter - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4193-4200 - range map product
		4093MH002270001404278R00	4227	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4163-4170 - best focus image product
		4093MH002270001404285R00	4228	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4163-4170 - range map product
		4093MH002270001404295R00	4229	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4153-4160 - best focus image product
		4093MH002270001404305R00	4230	target Iridescent_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4093 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4153-4160 - range map product

Sol 4098 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-Feb-24
camera position	44
total parent images	44
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	50

MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Horseshoe_Meadows, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4098MH00190001404232C0D	4231	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4098MH00190001404232C0D	4232	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4098MH00168001404232C0D	4233	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4098MH00168001404234C0D	4234	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4098MH00168001404235C0D	4235	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404236C0D	4236	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404237C0D	4237	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404238C0D	4238	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404239C0D	4239	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404240C0D	4240	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404241C0D	4241	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404242C0D	4242	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4098MH00168001404243C0D	4243	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4098MH00168001404244C0D	4244	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4098MH00168001404245C0D	4245	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404246C0D	4246	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404247C0D	4247	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404248C0D	4248	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404249C0D	4249	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404250C0D	4250	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404251C0D	4251	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00168001404252C0D	4252	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4098MH00743001404253C0D	4253	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4098MH00743001404254C0D	4254	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4098MH00743001404255C0D	4255	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404256C0D	4256	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404257C0D	4257	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404258C0D	4258	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404259C0D	4259	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404260C0D	4260	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404261C0D	4261	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4098MH00743001404262C0D	4262	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00866	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT MAHLI prox mode ~5 cm standoff	4098MH00866001404263C0D	4263	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 5 cm
mN00867	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff	4098MH00867001404264C0D	4264	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 5 cm
mN00868	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT MAHLI prox mode ~3 cm standoff	4098MH00868001404265C0D	4265	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00869	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT MAHLI prox mode ~2 cm standoff	4098MH00869001404266C0D	4266	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00870	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT MAHLI prox mode ~15 mm standoff	4098MH00870001404267C0D	4267	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm
mN00871	Horseshoe_Meadows after DRT MAHLI prox mode ~1 cm standoff	4098MH00871001404268C0D	4268	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm
mN00193	Focus Merges	4098MH00193001404269C0D	4269	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm
		4098MH00193001404270C0D	4270	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm
		4098MH00193001404271C0D	4271	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 15 mm
		4098MH00193001404272C0D	4272	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 15 mm
		4098MH00193001404273C0D	4273	autofocus sub-frame for target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 1 cm
		4098MH00193001404274C0D	4274	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 1 cm
mN00193	Focus Merges	4098MH00193001404275R0D	4275	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4098 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4255-4262 - best focus image product
		4098MH00193001404276R0D	4276	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4098 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4255-4262 - range map product
		4098MH00193001404277R0D	4277	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4098 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4245-4252 - best focus image product
		4098MH00193001404278R0D	4278	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4098 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4245-4252 - range map product
mN00193	Focus Merges	4098MH00193001404279R0D	4279	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4098 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4235-4242 - best focus image product
		4098MH00193001404280R0D	4280	target Horseshoe_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4098 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4235-4242 - range map product

updated: 08_March_2024

Sol 4101 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Feb-24
camera position	7
total parent images	45
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	45

MAHLI imaged the REMS UV sensor, the target Thunderbolt_Peak and the target Tenderfoot_Peak.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose [RATIONAL, DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit]
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~25 cm standoff	4101MH00095001404281C0D	4281	autoFocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		4101MH00095001404282C0D	4282	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00199	Thunderbolt_Peak ~25 cm standoff	4101MH00199001404283C0D	4283	autoFocus sub-frame for target Thunderbolt_Peak - standoff near 25 cm
		4101MH00199001404284C0D	4284	target Thunderbolt_Peak - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Thunderbolt_Peak stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4101MH00182001404285C0D	4285	autoFocus sub-frame for target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404286C0D	4286	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404287C0D	4287	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404288C0D	4288	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404289C0D	4289	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404290C0D	4290	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404291C0D	4291	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404292C0D	4292	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404293C0D	4293	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404294C0D	4294	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Thunderbolt_Peak stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4101MH00182001404295C0D	4295	autoFocus sub-frame for target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404296C0D	4296	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404297C0D	4297	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404298C0D	4298	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404299C0D	4299	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404300C0D	4300	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404301C0D	4301	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404302C0D	4302	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404303C0D	4303	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404304C0D	4304	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00199	Tenderfoot_Peak ~25 cm standoff	4101MH00199001404305C0D	4305	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tenderfoot_Peak - standoff near 25 cm
		4101MH00199001404306C0D	4306	target Tenderfoot_Peak - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Tenderfoot_Peak stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4101MH00182001404307C0D	4307	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404308C0D	4308	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404309C0D	4309	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404310C0D	4310	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404311C0D	4311	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404312C0D	4312	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404313C0D	4313	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404314C0D	4314	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404315C0D	4315	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404316C0D	4316	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Tenderfoot_Peak stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4101MH00182001404317C0D	4317	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404318C0D	4318	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4101MH00182001404319C0D	4319	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404320C0D	4320	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404321C0D	4321	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404322C0D	4322	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404323C0D	4323	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404324C0D	4324	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404325C0D	4325	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4101MH00182001404326C0D	4326	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 21_February_2024

Sol 4102 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Feb-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4101 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100013	Focus Merges	4102MH001530001404327900	4327	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4319-4326 - best focus image product
		4102MH001530001404328500	4328	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4319-4326 - range map product
		4102MH001530001404329900	4329	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4309-4316 - best focus image product
		4102MH001530001404330500	4330	target Tenderfoot_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4309-4316 - range map product
		4102MH001530001404331900	4331	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4297-4304 - best focus image product
		4102MH001530001404332500	4332	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4297-4304 - range map product
		4102MH001530001404333900	4333	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4287-4294 - best focus image product
		4102MH001530001404334500	4334	target Thunderbolt_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4101 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4287-4294 - range map product

updated: 25_April_2024

Sol 4106 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Feb-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	11
total focus merge products	22
total parent images + focus merge products	22
summary of MAHLI activities	Focus stack images from Sol 4105 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mH00449	Focus Merges	4106MH00049000140449300	4449	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4439-4446 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140445000	4450	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4439-4446 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140445100	4451	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4429-4436 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140445200	4452	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4429-4436 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140445300	4453	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4419-4426 - Best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140445400	4454	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4419-4426 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140445500	4455	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4409-4416 - Best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140445600	4456	intended Mineral_King drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4409-4416 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140445700	4457	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 7 of 7 - standoff beyond 50 cm - image not in focus - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4377-4384 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140445800	4458	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 7 of 7 - standoff beyond 50 cm - image not in focus - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4377-4384 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140445900	4459	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 6 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4377-4384 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140446000	4460	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 6 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4377-4384 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140446100	4461	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 5 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4377-4384 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140446200	4462	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 5 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4377-4384 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140446300	4463	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 4 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4367-4374 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140446400	4464	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 4 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4367-4374 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140446500	4465	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 3 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4357-4364 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140446600	4466	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 3 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4357-4364 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140446700	4467	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 2 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4347-4354 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140446800	4468	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 2 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4347-4354 - range map product
		4106MH00049000140446900	4469	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 1 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4337-4344 - best focus image product
		4106MH00049000140447000	4470	target Observation_Peak - mosaic position 1 of 7 - standoff between 27 cm and 43 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4105 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4337-4344 - range map product

updated: 11_March_2024

Sol 4116 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-Mar-24
camera position	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the Mineral_King drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Mineral_King drill hole drilled on Sol 4107 ~24 cm standoff	4116MH0001970001404473C00	4471	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Mineral_King - drilled sol 4107 - standoff near 24 cm
		4116MH0001970011404473C00	4472	drill hole in rock named Mineral_King - drilled sol 4107 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00274	Mineral_King drill hole drilled on Sol 4107 ~95 mm standoff	4116MH0007740001404473C00	4473	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Mineral_King - drilled sol 4107 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 95 mm
		4116MH0007740011404473C00	4474	drill hole in rock named Mineral_King - drilled sol 4107 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 95 mm
mN00152	Mineral_King drill cuttings APXS spot 1 ~4 cm standoff	4116MH0001520001404473C00	4475	autofocus sub-frame for Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4116MH0001520011404473C00	4476	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4116MH0001520021404473C00	4477	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520031404473C00	4478	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520041404473C00	4479	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520051404480C00	4480	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520061404480C00	4481	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520071404482C00	4482	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520081404483C00	4483	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520091404484C00	4484	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Mineral_King drill cuttings APXS spot 2 ~4 cm standoff	4116MH0001520001404485C00	4485	autofocus sub-frame for Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4116MH0001520011404486C00	4486	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4116MH0001520021404487C00	4487	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520031404488C00	4488	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520041404489C00	4489	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520051404490C00	4490	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520061404491C00	4491	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520071404492C00	4492	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520081404493C00	4493	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4116MH0001520091404494C00	4494	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	4116MH0002650001404495R00	4495	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4116 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4487-4494 - best focus image product
		4116MH0002650001404496S00	4496	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4116 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4487-4494 - range map product
		4116MH0002650001404497R00	4497	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4116 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4477-4484 - best focus image product
		4116MH0002650001404498S00	4498	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4116 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4477-4484 - range map product

updated: 11_March_2024

Sol 4117 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6 Mar 24
camera positions	5
total parent images	5
focus merges performed	0
total parent merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	5

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Mineral_King drill hole cuttings. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Mineral_King drill cuttings APXS spot 1 ~ 5 cm standoff	4117MH00122001404499C00	4499	autoFocus sub-frame for Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4117MH001220011404500C00	4500	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	Mineral_King drill cuttings APXS spot 2 ~ 5 cm standoff	4117MH00122001404501C00	4501	autoFocus sub-frame for Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4117MH001220011404502C00	4502	Mineral_King drill cuttings - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	4117MH000312001404503C00	4503	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		4117MH0003120011404504C00	4504	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	4117MH000326001404505C00	4505	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	4117MH000326001404506C00	4506	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00328	~19 cm above open CheMin inlet	4117MH000280001404507C00	4507	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 11_March_2024

Sol 4118 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	7_Mar_24	
		camera position	6	Image ID:
		total parent images	45	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	53	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mineral_King2 after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000190	Mineral_King2 after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4118MH000190000140450800	4508	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4118MH000190001404509000	4509	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN000168	Mineral_King2 after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4118MH000168000140451000	4510	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4118MH000168001404511000	4511	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4118MH000168002140451200	4512	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451300	4513	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451400	4514	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451500	4515	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451600	4516	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451700	4517	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451800	4518	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140451900	4519	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000168	Mineral_King2 after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4118MH000168000140452000	4520	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4118MH000168001404521000	4521	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4118MH000168002140452200	4522	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452300	4523	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452400	4524	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452500	4525	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452600	4526	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452700	4527	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452800	4528	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140452900	4529	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000302	Mineral_King2 after DRT APXS spot 2 ~2 cm standoff	4118MH000302000140453000	4530	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		4118MH000302001404531000	4531	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		4118MH000302002140453200	4532	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453300	4533	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453400	4534	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453500	4535	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453600	4536	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453700	4537	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453800	4538	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000302002140453900	4539	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000168	Mineral_King2 after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4118MH000168000140454000	4540	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4118MH000168001404541000	4541	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4118MH000168002140454200	4542	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454300	4543	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454400	4544	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454500	4545	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454600	4546	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454700	4547	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454800	4548	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4118MH000168002140454900	4549	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000465	Mineral_King2 after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	4118MH000465000140455000	4550	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King2 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4118 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		4118MH000465001140455100	4551	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4118 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN000153	Focus Merges	4118MH000153000140455200	4552	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4542-4549 - best focus image product
		4118MH000153000140455300	4553	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4542-4549 - range map product
		4118MH000153000140455400	4554	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4532-4539 - best focus image product
		4118MH000153000140455500	4555	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4532-4539 - range map product
		4118MH000153000140455600	4556	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4522-4529 - best focus image product
		4118MH000153000140455700	4557	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4522-4529 - range map product
		4118MH000153000140455800	4558	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4512-4519 - best focus image product
		4118MH000153000140455900	4559	intended Mineral_King2 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4118 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4512-4519 - range map product

updated: 15_March_2024

Sol 4123 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	12-Mar-24	
		camera position	6	Image ID:
		total parent images	44	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	52	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mineral_King3 after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000190	Mineral_King3 after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4123MH0001900001404560C00	4560	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4123MH000190001404561C00	4561	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN000168	Mineral_King3 after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4123MH0001680001404562C00	4562	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4123MH000168001404563C00	4563	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4123MH0001680021404564C00	4564	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404565C00	4565	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404566C00	4566	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404567C00	4567	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404568C00	4568	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404569C00	4569	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404570C00	4570	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404571C00	4571	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000168	Mineral_King3 after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4123MH0001680001404572C00	4572	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4123MH000168001404573C00	4573	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4123MH0001680021404574C00	4574	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404575C00	4575	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404576C00	4576	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404577C00	4577	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404578C00	4578	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404579C00	4579	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404580C00	4580	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404581C00	4581	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000743	Mineral_King3 after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	4123MH0007430001404582C00	4582	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4123MH000743001404583C00	4583	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4123MH0007430021404584C00	4584	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404585C00	4585	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404586C00	4586	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404587C00	4587	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404588C00	4588	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404589C00	4589	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404590C00	4590	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0007430021404591C00	4591	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000168	Mineral_King3 after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4123MH0001680001404592C00	4592	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4123MH000168001404593C00	4593	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4123MH0001680021404594C00	4594	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404595C00	4595	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404596C00	4596	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404597C00	4597	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404598C00	4598	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4123MH0001680021404599C00	4599	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000465	Mineral_King3 after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	4123MH0004650001404600C00	4602	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mineral_King3 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4123 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		4123MH0004650011404603C00	4603	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4123 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN000153	Focus Merges	4123MH0001530001404604C00	4604	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4594-4601 - best focus image product
		4123MH0001530001404605C00	4605	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4594-4601 - range map product
		4123MH0001530001404606C00	4606	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4584-4591 - best focus image product
		4123MH0001530001404607C00	4607	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4584-4591 - range map product
		4123MH0001530001404608C00	4608	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4574-4581 - best focus image product
		4123MH0001530001404609C00	4609	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4574-4581 - range map product
		4123MH0001530001404610C00	4610	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4564-4571 - best focus image product
		4123MH0001530001404611C00	4611	intended Mineral_King3 drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4123 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4564-4571 - range map product

updated: 27_August_2024

Sol 4127 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Mar-24
camera position	0
total parent images	15
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the attempted (Sol 4125) Mineral_King3 drill hole and drill cuttings.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002197	Mineral_King3 drill hole attempt drilled on Sol 4125 ~25 cm standoff	4127MH0001970001404612C00	4612	autoFocus sub-frame for attempted drill hole in rock named Mineral_King3 - drilled sol 4125 - standoff near 25 cm
		4127MH0001970011404613C00	4613	attempted drill hole in rock named Mineral_King3 - drilled sol 4125 - standoff near 25 cm
mN002774	Mineral_King3 drill hole attempt drilled on Sol 4125 ~10 cm standoff	4127MH0007740001404614C00	4614	autoFocus sub-frame for attempted drill hole in rock named Mineral_King3 - drilled sol 4125 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 10 cm
		4127MH0007740011404615C00	4615	attempted drill hole in rock named Mineral_King3 - drilled sol 4125 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 10 cm
mN002999	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings after sol 4125 drill attempt ~4 cm standoff	4127MH000299001404616C00	4616	autoFocus sub-frame for Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm
		4127MH0002990011404617C00	4617	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm
		4127MH0002990021404618C00	4618	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4127MH0002990011404619C00	4619	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4127MH0002990021404620C00	4620	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4127MH0002990011404621C00	4621	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4127MH0002990021404622C00	4622	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4127MH0002990011404623C00	4623	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4127MH0002990021404624C00	4624	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4127MH0002990011404625C00	4625	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 27_August_2024

Sol 4128 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		17-Mar-24		
camera position:	3	Image ID:		
total parent images:	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	1	CCPFD:		
total focus merge products:	2	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	4			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the attempted (Sol 4125) Mineral_King3 drill cuttings. The focus stack images from Sol 4127 were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CCPFD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings after sol 4125 drill attempt ~5 cm standoff	4128MH001120001404626C00	4626	autoFocus sub-frame for Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 5 cm
		4128MH001120011404627C00	4627	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 5 cm
mN00258	Focus Merge	4128MH001258001404628R00	4628	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4127 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4618-4625 - best focus image product
		4128MH001258001404629S00	4629	Mineral_King3 drill cuttings - after sol 4125 drill attempt - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4127 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4618-4625 - range map product

updated: 27_August_2024

Sol 4130 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	19-Mar-24	
		camera position	53	Image ID:
		total parent images	5	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	58	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Tunnel_View and acquired a 2x1 mosaic on the target Cardinal_Mountain. The focus stack images were merged as well.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Tunnel_View after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4130MH00190001404630C020	4630	autofocus sub-frame for target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4130MH00190001404631C020	4631	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00268	Tunnel_View after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4130MH001680021404632C020	4632	autofocus sub-frame for target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4130MH001680021404633C020	4633	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4130MH001680021404634C020	4634	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404635C020	4635	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404636C020	4636	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404637C020	4637	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404638C020	4638	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404639C020	4639	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404640C020	4640	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404641C020	4641	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Tunnel_View after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4130MH001680021404642C020	4642	autofocus sub-frame for target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4130MH001680021404643C020	4643	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4130MH001680021404644C020	4644	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404645C020	4645	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404646C020	4646	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404647C020	4647	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404648C020	4648	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404649C020	4649	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404650C020	4650	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH001680021404651C020	4651	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Tunnel_View after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4130MH000743001404652C020	4652	autofocus sub-frame for target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4130MH000743001404653C020	4653	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4130MH000743001404654C020	4654	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404655C020	4655	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404656C020	4656	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404657C020	4657	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404658C020	4658	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404659C020	4659	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404660C020	4660	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000743001404661C020	4661	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Cardinal_Mountain mosaic position 1 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	4130MH000865001404662C020	4662	autofocus sub-frame for target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4130MH000865001404663C020	4663	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4130MH000865001404664C020	4664	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH000865001404665C020	4665	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304666C020	4666	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304667C020	4667	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304668C020	4668	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304669C020	4669	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304670C020	4670	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304671C020	4671	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Cardinal_Mountain mosaic position 2 of 2 ~24 cm standoff	4130MH0008650011304672C020	4672	autofocus sub-frame for target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4130MH0008650011304673C020	4673	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4130MH0008650011304674C020	4674	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304675C020	4675	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304676C020	4676	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304677C020	4677	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304678C020	4678	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304679C020	4679	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304680C020	4680	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4130MH0008650011304681C020	4681	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	4130MH0002270011304682R020	4682	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4674-4681 - best focus image product
		4130MH0002270011304683R020	4683	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4674-4681 - range map product
		4130MH0002270011304684R020	4684	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4664-4671 - best focus image product
		4130MH0002270011304685R020	4685	target Cardinal_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4664-4671 - range map product
		4130MH0002270011304686R020	4686	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 3 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4634-4661 - best focus image product
		4130MH0002270011304687R020	4687	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 3 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4634-4661 - range map product
		4130MH0002270011304688R020	4688	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4644-4651 - best focus image product
		4130MH0002270011304689R020	4689	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4644-4651 - range map product
		4130MH0002270011304690R020	4690	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4634-4661 - best focus image product
		4130MH0002270011304691R020	4691	target Tunnel_View - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4130 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4634-4661 - range map product

Sol 4132 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21-Mar-24	
		camera position	7	Image ID:
		total parent images:	63	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	6	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	13	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	74	
MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Three_Teeth_Doodad and the target Col_de_Doodad. The focus stack images were merged as well.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Three_Teeth_Doodad after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4132MH001900001204692C00	4692	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH00190001204693C00	4693	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00336	Three_Teeth_Doodad after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4132MH003360001204694C00	4694	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4132MH00336001204695C00	4695	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4132MH003360021204696C00	4696	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360031204697C00	4697	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360041204698C00	4698	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360051204699C00	4699	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360061204700C00	4700	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360071204701C00	4701	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360081204702C00	4702	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360091204703C00	4703	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Three_Teeth_Doodad after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4132MH003360001204704C00	4704	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4132MH00336001204705C00	4705	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4132MH003360021204706C00	4706	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360031204707C00	4707	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360041204708C00	4708	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360051204709C00	4709	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360061204710C00	4710	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360071204711C00	4711	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360081204712C00	4712	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH003360091204713C00	4713	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Three_Teeth_Doodad after DRT stereo-1 ~1 cm standoff	4132MH008640001204714C00	4714	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4132MH008640011204715C00	4715	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4132MH008640021204716C00	4716	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640031204717C00	4717	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640041204718C00	4718	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640051204719C00	4719	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640061204720C00	4720	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640071204721C00	4721	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640081204722C00	4722	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008640091204723C00	4723	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Col_de_Doodad stereo-1 ~24 cm standoff	4132MH008650001204724C00	4724	autofocus sub-frame for target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH008650011204725C00	4725	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH008650021204726C00	4726	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650031204727C00	4727	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650041204728C00	4728	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650051204729C00	4729	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650061204730C00	4730	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650071204731C00	4731	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650081204732C00	4732	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650091204733C00	4733	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Col_de_Doodad stereo-2 ~24 cm standoff	4132MH008650001204734C00	4734	autofocus sub-frame for target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH008650011204735C00	4735	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH008650021204736C00	4736	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650031204737C00	4737	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650041204738C00	4738	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650051204739C00	4739	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650061204740C00	4740	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650071204741C00	4741	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650081204742C00	4742	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650091204743C00	4743	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Col_de_Doodad stereo-3 ~24 cm standoff	4132MH008650001204744C00	4744	autofocus sub-frame for target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH008650011204745C00	4745	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4132MH008650021204746C00	4746	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650031204747C00	4747	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650041204748C00	4748	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650051204749C00	4749	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650061204750C00	4750	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650071204751C00	4751	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650081204752C00	4752	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4132MH008650091204753C00	4753	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mnh00163	Focus Merge	4132MH00163001004754900	4754	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4746-4753 - best focus image product
		4132MH00163001004755500	4755	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4746-4753 - range map product
		4132MH00163001004756900	4756	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4736-4743 - best focus image product
		4132MH00163001004757500	4757	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4736-4743 - range map product
		4132MH00163001004758900	4758	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4726-4733 - best focus image product
		4132MH00163001004759500	4759	target Col_de_Doodad - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4726-4733 - range map product
		4132MH00163001004760900	4760	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4716-4723 - best focus image product
		4132MH00163001004761500	4761	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4716-4723 - range map product
		4132MH00163001004762900	4762	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4706-4713 - best focus image product
		4132MH00163000904763500	4763	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4706-4713 - range map product
		4132MH00163000904764900	4764	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4696-4703 - best focus image product
		4132MH00163000904765500	4765	target Three_Teeth_Doodad - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4132 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4696-4703 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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References

- Anderson, R. C., L. W. Beegle, J. Hurowitz, C. Hanson, W. Abbey, C. Seybold, D. Limonadi, S. Kuhn, L. Jandura, K. Brown, G. Peters, C. Roumeliotis, M. Robinson, K. Edgett, M. Minitti, J. Grotzinger (2015) The Mars Science Laboratory scooping campaign at Rocknest, *Icarus* 256, 66–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2015.03.033>
- Edgett, K. S., R. A. Yingst, M. A. Ravine, M. A. Caplinger, J. N. Maki, F. T. Ghaemi, J. A. Schaffner, J. F. Bell III, L. J. Edwards, K. E. Herkenhoff, E. Heydari, L. C. Kah, M. T. Lemmon, M. E. Minitti, T. S. Olson, T. J. Parker, S. K. Rowland, J. Schieber, R. J. Sullivan, D. Y. Sumner, P. C. Thomas, E. H. Jensen, J. J. Simmonds, A. J. Sengstacken, R. G. Willson, and W. Goetz (2012) Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) investigation, *Space Sci. Rev.* 170, 259–317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-012-9910-4>
- Edgett, K. S., R. A. Yingst, and the MSL Science Team (2013) Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI): Sol 0–179 activities, observations, range and scale characterization, *European Planetary Science Congress 2013*, vol. 8, Abstract EPSC2013-246. (8–13 September 2013, London, United Kingdom)
- Edgett, K. S., M. A. Caplinger, J. N. Maki, M. A. Ravine, F. T. Ghaemi, S. McNair, K. E. Herkenhoff, B. M. Duston, R. G. Willson, R. A. Yingst, M. R. Kennedy, M. E. Minitti, A. J. Sengstacken, K. D. Supulver, L. J. Lipkaman, G. M. Krezoski, M. J. McBride, T. L. Jones, B. E. Nixon, J. K. Van Beek, D. J. Krysak, and R. L. Kirk (2015) Curiosity's robotic arm-mounted Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI): Characterization and calibration status, *MSL MAHLI Technical Report 0001* (version 1: 19 June 2015; version 2: 05 October 2015). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>
- Garvin, J. B., K. S. Edgett, R. Dotson, D. M. Fey, K. E. Herkenhoff, B. J. Hallet, M. R. Kennedy (2017) Quantitative relief models of rock surfaces on Mars at sub-millimeter scales from Mars Curiosity rover Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) observations: Geologic implications, *Microscopy and Microanalysis* 23(S1), 2146–2147. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927617011394>
- Malin, M., Edgett, K., Jensen, E., Lipkaman, L. (2013) Mast Camera (Mastcam), Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI), and Mars Descent Imager (MARDI) Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) PDS data products, version 1.2, *Mars Science Laboratory Project Software Interface Specification (SIS)*, JPL D-75410, SIS-

SCI0135-MSL, file MSL_MMM_EDR_RDR_DPSIS.PDF archived by the NASA Planetary Data System, 29 October 2013.

- Minitti, M. E., L. C. Kah, R. A. Yingst, K. S. Edgett, R. C. Anderson, L. W. Beegle, J. L. Carsten, R. G. Deen, W. Goetz, C. Hardgrove, D. E. Harker, K. E. Herkenhoff, J. A. Hurowitz, L. Jandura, M. R. Kennedy, G. Kocurek, G. M. Krezoski, S. R. Kuhn, D. Limonadi, L. Lipkaman, M. B. Madsen, T. S. Olson, M. L. Robinson, S. K. Rowland, D. M. Rubin, C. Seybold, J. Schieber, M. Schmidt, D. Y. Sumner, V. V. Tompkins, J. K. Van Beek, T. Van Beek (2013) MAHLI at the Rocknest sand shadow: Science and science-enabling activities, *J. Geophys. Res.* 118(11), 2338–2360. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JE004426>
- Vasavada, A. R., J. P. Grotzinger, R. E. Arvidson, F. J. Calef, J. A. Crisp, S. Gupta, J. Hurowitz, N. Mangold, S. Maurice, M. E. Schmidt, R. C. Wiens, R. M. E. Williams, and R. A. Yingst (2014) Overview of the Mars Science Laboratory mission: Bradbury Landing to Yellowknife Bay and beyond, *J. Geophys. Res.* 119, 1134–1161. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JE004622>
- Yingst, R. A., K. S. Edgett, M. R. Kennedy, G. M. Krezoski, M. J. McBride, M. E. Minitti, M. A. Ravine, R. M. E. Williams (2016) MAHLI on Mars: Lessons learned operating a geoscience camera on a landed payload robotic arm, *Geoscientific Instrumentation, Methods and Data Systems* 5, 205–217. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-5-205-2016>

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